

PRENATAL AND PERINATAL PSYCHOLOGY:
A REVIEW OF THE HISTORY, PRINCIPLES, CLINICAL FINDINGS, SCIENTIFIC
BASIS AND APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology: A Review of the History, Clinical Findings, Scientific Basis, Principles, and Applications

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Prenatal and perinatal psychology (PPN) has been evolving as a multidisciplinary field in psychology for the past 30 years. This field explores how our most early experiences - from conception through gestation, birth and early infancy, influence and shape our entire lives. Over the years, findings from clinical prenatal and perinatal oriented work with infants, children and adults have challenged our assumptions regarding early human development, and given us a new understanding of the capacities and capabilities of unborn babies and infants; however, research is just beginning to support these findings. Despite the field's expansion in the last decade, its new discoveries have remained largely unavailable to the public, particularly in countries other than the United States. As a result, people in non-English speaking countries have limited access to the important discoveries of PPN. Israel, in which the spoken language is Hebrew, is one of these countries. In order to make the information about PPN available to the Israeli public, this literature review will culminate in the provision of a Hebrew-language internet resource for the Israeli public at home and abroad.

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Introduction

A multidisciplinary field has been emerging in psychology over the past 30 years – the field of prenatal and perinatal psychology (PPN). PPN explores how our early experiences from conception through the first few years following birth, influence and shape our entire lives (Lyman, 2006, 2007). The field originally sprung from clinical findings and anecdotal records of European and American psychoanalysts and psychotherapists who practiced independently throughout the 1900's (Chamberlain, 2001; Contey, 2006; Ridgeway & House 2006; Schindler, 2000). These therapists consistently found that clients had memories of their prenatal and birth experiences and that many of their current psychological problems were resolved once these memories were brought to consciousness and processed (Contey, 2006).

Besides having direct implications for psychotherapy, these findings challenged the prevailing assumptions regarding early human development as they pointed to the possibility that unborn babies and infants were conscious, aware and able to remember (Chamberlain, 1999; Contey, 2006). During the 1970's and 1980's, many of these practitioners joined together to form professional associations, to share their findings and validate them scientifically (Chamberlain, 2000; Contey, 2006; Ridgeway & House 2006; Schindler, 2000).

By gathering and integrating information from scientific research in embryology, cell biology, neuroscience, and from direct fetal observations made possible by ultrasound and intrauterine photography, these practitioners began to form the knowledge base of a newly emerging field (Chamberlain, 1999). Their goal was to consolidate the field of PPN, which was exclusively based on practitioner experience and belief, as an

empirical discourse based on science (Lyman, 2006). This effort was taken a step further in 2000 with the foundation of the Santa Barbara Graduate Institute (SBGI), the first graduate school to offer masters and doctoral degrees in counseling and clinical psychology with a specialty in PPN (Contey, 2006).

The purpose of this literature review is twofold. First, it offers graduate students in the field of PPN a comprehensive and updated review of the field. When students gain a clear understanding of how their field of study has evolved and its current status, I believe they are better able to make choices regarding necessary future study and research in the field. Second, this literature review will serve as a knowledge base for the first internet resource about PPN in Hebrew.

I have divided the literature review into six sections. The first section gives a broad definition of PPN. The second depicts the history of the field starting with its early precursors, dating back to the beginning of the 20th century, and followed by a description of the main historical events that have taken place in its evolution in the past 30 years. The main principles of PPN are summarized in the third section. The fourth section presents the major pioneers of the field, highlights their clinical work, and delineates their foundational findings, while the fifth reviews the scientific evidence that supports these clinical findings. Last, two major areas of application of the field of PPN are discussed: prenatal health and prenatal parenting.

Review of the Literature

A Definition of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

The prenatal and perinatal period of human development includes conception, gestation, birth and early infancy (Santa Barbara Graduate Institute, 2007). Prenatal and

perinatal psychology (PPN) examines the psychological implications of the individual's experience during this early period. Central to the field is the acknowledgement of the significant role prenatal and perinatal experiences, particularly traumatic ones, play in the shaping of personality and future psychological development (Lyman, 2006).

PPN is both a field of study and a psychotherapeutic practice. As a field of study, PPN is multidisciplinary. It encompasses research on attachment, clinical psychology, embryology, neurobiology, and cellular biology (Santa Barbara Graduate Institute, 2007). Findings from these research fields are integrated and assimilated in order to shed light on the formative impact early experiences have on the individual. As a psychotherapeutic practice, PPN is considered an integrative approach. It incorporates different traditional therapy modalities such as psychodynamic, Gestalt, behavioral, cognitive, humanistic-existential, and somatic (Lyman, 2006; Santa Barbara Graduate Institute, 2007) as well as various innovative therapeutic techniques (Emerson, 1989).

A prenatal and perinatal approach could be applied within individual therapy or a group context (Glenn, 2002) and prenatal and perinatal therapists conduct psychotherapy with infants, children, adolescents, adults and families (Santa Barbara Graduate Institute, 2007). A fundamental belief in PPN is that the way to heal distressing problems in the present is by revealing their origins in the prenatal and perinatal period and making a conscious connection between past traumatic memories and present concerns. As Lyman (2007) explains:

Client and therapist work to change the emotional charge that accompanies the early memories. In this way, the feelings are processed, integrated, and new ways

of being can take place. It is by connecting the past to the present that the story is complete and the missing pieces are filled. (p. 29)

The History of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

Contey (2006) has given a fine account of the history of PPN in which she makes a distinction between the early precursors of the field, dating back to the beginning of the 20th century, and the history of the field as it has evolved in the past 30 years. In the following section I will review her account by highlighting the key historical events of PPN, in order to set the context for the evolution of this field.

Early Precursors of the Field

During the early 1900's European and American psychotherapists who practiced with adults began noticing that their patients had actual "memories" of their prenatal and birth experiences and that these early memories distinctly affected their life. When these memories were brought to consciousness and processed, many of the psychological and physical problems patients suffered from were resolved. Although these therapists, ranging from psychoanalysts, physicians, and psychiatrists, practiced independently and used various treatment modalities, such as traditional psychoanalysis, controlled drug therapy, and breathe work, their findings were quite consistent and have contributed to the development of the theoretical framework of PPN (Contey, 2006).

Contey (2006) mentions Sigmund Freud as the first to propose that birth could have a lasting psychological impact on the individual. In the second edition of his book *The Interpretation of Dreams* Freud added a footnote stating that "the act of birth is the first experience of anxiety, and thus the source and prototype of the affect of anxiety" (Freud, 1990/ 1994, p. 436). According to Contey, Freud initially attributed asphyxia, the

sensation of suffocation as a result of lack of oxygen, to the trauma experienced by the baby at birth; however, later he explained birth memory as fantasy.

Otto Rank, Freud's student and protégé, expanded on his teacher's view of birth and developed a theory that all neurosis originates in the trauma of birth (Ridgway & House, 2006). This theory was the subject of Rank's book *The Trauma of Birth* which was published in 1929. Rank believed that life in the womb is blissful and pleasurable and that birth was an inherently traumatic event because of the inevitable separation from the "paradise" environment of the womb (Contey, 2006; Ridgway & House, 2006). Contey (2006) explains that unlike Freud, Rank believed that birth trauma was a result of real experience and not fantasy and that this trauma could be accessed and resolved through psychotherapy.

In fear that his work would be diminished by the importance attached to the trauma of birth, Freud was convinced by others to reject Rank's theory. Rank was thrown out of Freud's inner circle and the psychoanalytic community (Contey, 2006; Rhodes, 2003). This may also be the reason why Freud's footnote regarding the anxiety produced by birth was deleted from subsequent editions of *The Interpretation of Dreams* (Rhodes, 2003).

Although Rank has been named "the most famous of the early prenatal psychologists" (Ridgway & House, 2006, p.66), and his work has been considered seminal to the field of PPN, some aspects of his theory have been refuted by later findings regarding the unborn child's experience in the womb. Despite Rank's belief that the prenatal period was blissful, later evidence has shown that the prenatal period can in

fact contain traumatic experiences that could negatively impact the unborn child, just as he believed birth could (Rhodes, 2003).

Contey (2006) continues her review of the contributors by presenting the work of Nador Fodor who was Rank's student and a Hungarian psychoanalyst. Like Rank, Contey writes, Fodor acknowledged the traumatic effect of birth; however, he was one of the first theorists to suggest that events during the prenatal period could be traumatic for the unborn child (Adzema, 2004; Contey, 2006; Pre- and perinatal psychology, n.d.). Fodor believed many of his patients' dreams reflected birth and prenatal material. He comprised lists of symbols that recurred in his patients' dreams, which he believed related to the prenatal and perinatal period (Adzema, 2004; Ridgway & House, 2006). Fodor was the first clinician who discovered his patients had actual reenactments of birth. He designed therapeutic interventions aimed at processing prenatal memories and releasing the negative effects stemming from birth trauma (Adzema, 2004). According to Contey (2006), Fodor believed that a psychic or telepathic link between mother and baby was possible. His book *The Search for the Beloved: A Clinical Investigation of the Trauma of Birth and Pre-Natal Conditioning* was published in 1949 (Contey, 2006).

Francis Mott, an English Psychoanalyst and a student of Fodor, developed a system of fetal therapy with children and adults. His work with children comprised of physical birth reenactments. Like Fodor, Mott applied prenatal and perinatal concepts in his analysis of his patients' dreams (Contey, 2006). Adzema (2004) points out that Mott "traced consciousness back to events around conception and saw these events as instituting patterns affecting all later experience and conceptual constructions" (p. 31). Mott coined the term "negative umbilical affect", which relates to the transmission of

maternal distress through the umbilical to the unborn child. This concept was later expanded by Frank Lake (Contey, 2006; Ridgway & House, 2006).

Like her predecessors, Phyllis Greencare, an American psychoanalyst and physician, investigated the origins of anxiety and discussed the possibility that it was rooted in prenatal and perinatal experiences (Ridgway & House, 2006). According to Contey (2006), Greencare underscored the value of uncomplicated vaginal birth for the baby suggesting that “the challenges of labor and delivery serve as a ‘bridge’ between the protection and dependence of intrauterine life and the stress and independence of extrauterine life” (p. 23). Greencare also believed that birth leaves physical imprints in the body in the form of anxiety patterns, which are experienced later on in life as somatic reactions (Contey, 2006).

Elizabeth Fehr, also an American psychoanalyst, developed in the late 1960's *Natal Therapy* in order to treat her patients who exhibited repressed symptoms of birth trauma (Contey, 2006; Ridgway & House, 2006). Contey (2006) explains that natal therapy was performed in a group setting which included birth reenactments but also included verbal analytic interpretation during individual therapy. The basic assumption in Fehr's therapy was that the re-experiencing of the birth trauma could relieve the symptoms that were associated with early trauma. Leslie Feher, a counselor and Fehr's daughter, documented her mother's work and elaborated on it. In 1980, she published the book *The Psychology of Birth: Roots of Human Personality* (1980) in which she ascribes certain personality structures to specific birth experiences, such as assisted instrumental birth, caesarean delivery, breech birth and premature birth.

Contey (2006) includes Wilhelm Reich, Austrian psychiatrist and psychoanalyst, as a practitioner who contributed to the development of the field of PPN. According to Contey, Reich's ideas regarding the impact of the prenatal and perinatal period were quite avant-garde for his time; he believed that during this early period that the psychological constitution of the individual was established, and that an emotionally healthy mother provides the best uterine environment for the developing child. Reich warned against the use of medication during pregnancy and opposed modern birth practices, such as the use of drugs to sedate the mother during birth as he believed they "interfered with the innate 'self regulation' that could begin at birth if baby and mom were left to do what came naturally to both" (p. 23).

Both Reich and Mott's work influenced Frank Lake, a British physician and pastoral counselor (Contey, 2006). Lake was convinced that the origins of most of peoples' suffering could be traced back to their experiences during the prenatal and perinatal period, particularly to the first trimester, and even considered the idea that cellular memory could antedate brain memory (Contey, 2006; Ridgway & House, 2006). Before much was known about the drug, Lake used LSD as a therapeutic tool with his patients. In the mid 1940's, LSD was accidentally found to loosen one's state of consciousness, and shortly thereafter researchers and professionals – psychologists, psychiatrists as well as theologians and others - began implementing the drug in their work until it was banned from use in the United States in the 1960s (Ridgway & House, 2006).

Lake believed that under the influence of LSD his patients became conscious of early traumatic materials, such as birth trauma and early separation from the mother. As

these memories arose, it was possible to deal with them through therapy (Ridgway & House, 2006). He later abandoned the use of LSD and used Reichian-breathing techniques to regress his patients to the primal period (Contey, 2006).

Lake's work included both individual therapy sessions with patients and group work he referred to as "research group". The "research group", usually consisting of 20 patients, lasted a day or two and was facilitated by Lake and four tutors. Lake initially focused his attention on helping participants to get to know and trust each other and would then take notes of their histories and main complaints, "listening to any resonance with life in the womb" (House 2000, p. 216). Lake hung pictures of the reproductive journey on the wall and described the physiology of life in the womb to participants. Then the participants would break up into groups of four or five, and each person, lying down on a cushioned mattress, would be regressed, through facilitators' verbal cures, to conception and facilitated through the journey of life in the womb and the experience of birth (House, 2000). Lake's "research group" model has served as a prototype for prenatal and perinatal group processes developed later by various practitioners (Glenn, 2002).

Lake expanded Mott's idea of "negative umbilical affect" to a theory he called "maternal-fetal distress syndrome". The premise of this theory is that the baby can experience maternal emotions as early as the implantation period and is particularly sensitive to negative emotions, which are experienced as an invasion. The baby's reaction to negative affect has life long effects on personality and psychosomatic stress conditions, such as Asthma (Adzema, 2004; Contey, 2006; Ridgway & House, 2006). Contey (2006) writes that Lake believed in prioritizing the care of pregnant women on a

societal level as a way of creating a world of peace rather than a world of violence. This view is echoed throughout the field of PPN today and contains one of the major implications of this work for prenatal patient care.

Like Lake, Stanislav Grof, a Czechoslovakian psychiatrist, utilized LSD in his clinical work with patients in the 1950's, but later abandoned its use for a non-drug modality he called *Holotropic Breathwork* (Contey, 2006). In this technique, regression states are induced somatically through a variety of sounds, music, and movements (Adzema, 2004; Chamberlain, 1988). While he was still utilizing LSD in his work, Grof worked extensively with thousands of patients in regressed states and noticed that they would regularly relive their birth experiences. Grof believed that the physical, emotional, and spiritual experience of birth formed a psychological blueprint in the individual, later to affect the way he or she experiences life. Grof identified four basic patterns that recurred in his regressed patients who were born vaginally. He called these stages, which are roughly related to the four stages of birth, Basic Perinatal Matrices or BPMs (Adzema, 2004; Chamberlain, 1988; Contey, 2006; DeMause, 1982).

The first of the four BPMs is BPM I (Primal union with mother). BPM I represents the blissful or "oceanic" feelings that often characterize the fetus' state in the womb during early and mid pregnancy. BPM II (Antagonism with mother) is associated with the onset of labor. When the cervix is still closed, the fetus feels trapped as if there is "no exit," helpless, hopeless, and unable to move. BPM III (Synergism with mother) relates to the birth process itself. This stage is characterized by feelings of compression and suffering, but because there is movement and change, there is also hope of relief through struggle. Finally, BPM IV (Separation from mother) relates to the baby's entry

into the world, and the termination of the struggle. This stage is characterized by feelings of triumph, relief, and high, even manic elation (Adzema, 2004; Contey, 2006; Ridgway & House, 2006).

Contey (2006) goes on to describe Grof's theory of the *COEX System* as another contribution he made to the field. COEX (an abbreviation of COndensed EXperience) refers to the way the brain organizes experiences, either positive or negative, throughout life (Sharp & Sharp, 2009). A COEX system "consists of emotionally charged memories from different parts of our life that resemble each other in the quality of emotion or physical sensation that they share." (Grof, 2000, p. 22) Each COEX system revolves around a theme and the basic themes develop during the prenatal and perinatal period. As a system forms, later traumatic events build on top of early imprinted events, and unless treated and re-patterned, the COEX system will continue to evolve and influence the individual's belief systems for life (Castellino, 2000).

In the 1960's and the 1970's, new therapeutic techniques aimed at accessing early unconscious memories were developed by different practitioners. These techniques were primarily regressive techniques (Contey, 2006). In psychologist Arthur Janov's *Primal Scream Therapy*, also called *Primal Therapy*, patients recalled and reenacted a particularly disturbing early life experience, referred to as "primal pain." Patients expressed repressed anger or frustration through intensive means such as spontaneous and unrestrained screams, hysteria, or violence. As "primal pain", most often birth pain, was fully felt and processed, it would slowly become integrated by the patient (Chamberlain, 1988; Primal Scream Therapy, 2009).

Leonard Orr developed *Rebirthing-Breathwork*, a conscious breathing technique through which past traumatic experiences, including birth, are evoked (Chamberlain, 1988; Orr, n.d.). Orr (n.d.) claims that during the healing process, as patients re-experience their first breath, a transformation in their breathing mechanism and their mind-body-spirit relationship is notable. Hypnosis was another modality employed by professionals such as obstetrician David Cheek and psychologist David Chamberlain as a way to access unconscious memories of early prenatal and perinatal experiences. As these memories were brought to consciousness and processed during therapy, psychological problems would be resolved (Chamberlain, 1988; Contey, 2006).

Recent Development of the Field

For nearly a century, clinicians had been witnessing the fundamental impact of prenatal and perinatal life on the individual and the benefit of re-discovering, processing and integrating early experiences during therapy. Clinical evidence pointed to the possibility that unborn children and infants were conscious, aware and able to remember (Contey, 2006). These assumptions were contrary to mainstream beliefs regarding the capacities and capabilities of unborn children, governed by the 19th century held view of babies being “brainless, emotionless, and senseless” (Chamberlain, 1999, 2001). Furthermore, empirical research to support and explain such clinical findings was very preliminary at the time (Verny & Weintraub, 2002). For years, therefore, clinicians who included a prenatal and perinatal perspective in their work had difficulty in integrating their philosophy with the general public and mainstream psychologists (Ridgway & House, 2006).

Contey (2006) notes the initiation of the International Study Group for Prenatal Psychology (ISPP) by Austrian psychoanalyst Gustav Hans Garber in 1971, an important stage in the establishment of the field of PPN. This study group brought together clinicians and researchers interested in PPN. Garber, who was very enthusiastic about the transforming impact that birth and prenatal experiences had on the individual, was eager to establish an international dialogue on PPN (Schindler, 2000). Initially, members of the ISPP, known today as the International Society of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology and Medicine (ISPPM), included psychoanalysts, gynecologists, obstetricians, neonatologists, pediatricians and endocrinologists who were interested in the psychoneuroendocrinology of pregnancy of birth. Later, when primary prevention became the organization's main interest, non-medical birth professionals such as midwives and childbirth educators became included as members as well. Currently, the organization holds regular professional conferences internationally and publishes *The International Journal of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology and Medicine*, a quarterly journal (Contey, 2006).

The publication of the revolutionary book *The Secret Life of the Unborn Child* (Verny & Kelly, 1981) in the United States was pivotal to the evolution of the field of PPN. It set the stage for an ongoing process of consolidating PPN, which was exclusively based on practitioner experience and belief at the time, as an empirical discourse based on science. Verny and Kelly's seminal text not only presented anecdotal and clinical evidence of prenatal and perinatal experiences, but included evidence from experimental "traditional" scientific research demonstrating that babies were sensing and feeling, learning and remembering both in the womb and after birth. A new paradigm of early human development began to emerge (Chamberlain, 2000).

Both Chamberlain (2000) and Adzema (2004) state that it was Thomas Verny who was the actual stimulus for the new field of PPN. Chamberlain writes,

Thomas was the visionary who could see the emergence of an important new discipline that would require the attention of professionals from many different branches of study. He was the weaver who recognized the value of the separate strands of many contributors and was the first to weave them into one fabric.

Communicator that he was, Thomas reached out to everyone he could find who had similar interests and brought us together one by one. (p. 238)

Rejected in 1982 by the American Psychology Association to present findings from this emerging new field at the annual APA meeting, Verny and his colleagues decided to plan a conference of their own and in July 1983, the first International Congress on Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology was held. It was during the same year, and 12 years after the inception of the ISPPM in Europe, that Verny founded the Prenatal and Perinatal Association of North America (PPANA), later to become the Association of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology and Health (APPPAH). Chamberlain (2000) delineates the associations' declared goals:

The objectives of the Association were to further understand the psychology of pregnancy and birth and the ways in which pregnant mothers influence the unborn; to study the effects of medical intervention on mothers and babies; to explore remedial techniques to counteract pre- and perinatal traumas; to enhance the mental and physical health of mothers and fathers and their babies; to publish and distribute information; and to organize educational meetings for the purpose of exploring the above issues. (p. 240)

APPPAH members come from a variety of backgrounds and disciplines such as psychology, obstetrics, medicine, midwifery, pediatrics, anthropology, biology and holistic health. The association has been publishing a quarterly journal, the *Journal of Prenatal & Perinatal Psychology & Health*, since 1986 and has been organizing bi-annual conference since 1983 (Contey, 2006). Although ISPPM and APPPAH share a common vision, they remain mostly independent, apart from periodical sharing of research contributions between their journals (Rhodes, 2003).

The apparent benefits of prenatal and perinatal psychotherapy with adults led several practitioners, namely William Emerson, Raymond Castellino and Wendy Anne McCarty, during the 1980's and 1990's, to refocus their attention to therapeutic work with infants, children and their families. These clinicians developed different therapeutic interventions for supporting parents to help their children heal prenatal and perinatal trauma. In addition, through their work, they distilled a set of guiding principles for caring for newborns, which could be applied as preventative measures during the prenatal and perinatal stages of life, in order to avoid traumatic imprinting from occurring (Contey, 2006).

Recognizing the scarce academic research in the field and the growing need for professionals trained as prenatal and perinatal psychologists, Marti Glenn, Wendy Anne McCarty and Ken Bruer came to understand the urgency and importance of a formal academic program in prenatal and perinatal psychology. In 1999, the three united to found SBGI the first graduate school to offer masters and doctoral degrees in counseling and clinical psychology with a specialty in PPN (Contey, 2006; Glenn, n.d.).

Principles of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

McCarty and Glenn (2008) have distilled a set of twelve fundamental principles from the prenatal and perinatal lens, which unify professional, clinical and parental practices, including research, theory, and education. The principles define human beings as conscious, sentient, and aware during the primary period, a crucial time in human development in which one's core implicit patterns are formed. The principles underscore the capacities, capabilities, and basic needs of the human being during the primary period, as well as the lasting effect our most early relationships have on the quality of life and the baby's foundation. Healing unresolved early trauma, preferably prior to becoming parents, is highlighted as a way to enhance the quality of life for all family members.

Cited below, are the twelve principals as they appeared in McCarty and Glenn's (2008) article, *Primary psychology: Bridging the divide of early development*:

1. The Primary Period

The primary period for human development occurs from preconception through the first year of postnatal life. This is the time in which vital foundations are established at every level of being: physical, emotional, mental, spiritual and relational.

2. Forming the Core Blueprint

Experiences during this primary period form the blueprint of our core perceptions, belief structures, and ways of being in the world with others and ourselves.

These foundational elements are implicit, observable in newborns, and initiate life-long ways of being.

These core implicit patterns profoundly shape our being in life-enhancing or life-diminishing directions

3. Continuum of Development

Human development is continuous from prenatal to postnatal life. Postnatal patterns build upon earlier prenatal and birth experiences.

Optimal foundations for growth and resiliency, including brain development, emotional intelligence, and self-regulation are predicated upon optimal conditions during the pre-conception period, pregnancy, birth and the first year of life. Optimal foundations of secure attachment and healthy relationships are predicated upon optimal relationships during the pre-conception period, during pregnancy, the birth experience and the first year of life.

4. Capacities & Capabilities

Human beings are conscious, sentient, aware, and possess a sense of Self even during the very early primary period.

We seek ever-increasing states of wholeness and growth through the expression of human life. This innate drive guides and infuses our human development.

From the beginning of life, babies perceive, communicate, and learn in ways that include an integration of mind-to-mind, energetic, and physical-sensorial capacities and ways of being.

5. Relationships

Human development occurs within relationship from the beginning. Human connections and surrounding environment profoundly influence the quality and structure of every aspect of baby's development.

From the beginning of life, baby experiences and internalizes what mother experiences and feels. Father's and/or partner's relationship with mother and baby are integral to optimizing primary foundations for baby.

All relationships and encounters with mother, baby, and father during this primary period affect the quality of life and baby's foundation. Supportive loving and healthy relationships are integral to optimizing primary foundations for baby.

6. Innate Needs

The innate need for security, belonging, love and nurturing, feeling wanted, feeling valued, and being seen as the Self we are in present from the beginning of life.

Meeting these needs and providing the right environment supports optimal development.

7. Communication

Babies are continually communicating and seeking connection. Relating and responding to baby in ways that honor their multifaceted capacities for communication supports optimal development and wholeness.

8. Mother-Baby Interconnectedness

Respecting and optimizing the bond between mother and baby and the mother-baby interconnectedness during pregnancy, birth, and infancy is of highest priority.

9. Bonding

Birth and bonding is a critical developmental process for mother, baby, and father that form core patterns with life-long implications.

The best baby and mother outcomes occur when mother feels empowered and supported and the natural process of birth is allowed to unfold with minimal intervention and no interruption in mother-baby connection and physical contact. If any separation of baby from mother occurs, continuity of father's contact and connection with baby should be supported.

Baby responds and thrives best when the relationship with mother is undisturbed, when baby is communicated with directly, and when the process of birth supports baby's ability to orient and integrate the series of events.

10. Resolving & Healing

Resolving and healing past and current conflicts, stress, and issues that affect the quality of life for all family is of highest priority. Doing so before pregnancy is best. When needed, therapeutic support for mother, baby, and father provided as early as possible during this vital primary period is recommended for optimal outcomes.

11. Underlying Patterns

When unresolved issues remain or less than optimal conditions and experiences occur during conception, pregnancy, birth and the first postnatal year, life diminishing patterns often underlay health issues, stress behaviors, difficulty in self-regulation, attachment, learning, and other disorders over the life-span.

12. Professional Support

The early diminishing patterns embed below the level of conscious mind in the implicit memory system, subconscious, and somatic patterns. Professionals trained in primary psychology (prenatal and perinatal psychology) can identify these patterns and support babies, children, parents and adults to heal and shift these primary patterns to more life-enhancing ones at any age. When parents resolve and heal their own unresolved issues from their child's pregnancy and birth, their children benefit at any age. (pp. 2-4)

Clinical Work and Findings in Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

Over the years, practitioners from several disciplines have investigated the repercussions of early prenatal and perinatal experiences across the lifespan through their clinical work with infants, children and adults. Coming from various therapeutic fields, these practitioners have integrated their techniques with traditional methods in psychology to form a PPN clinical therapeutic approach. Their findings have contributed to the foundation of the major tenets of the field of PPN. In the following section I will present the major pioneers of the field and describe their clinical work and foundational findings.

Dr. David Chamberlain

Psychologist David Chamberlain began utilizing hypnosis with his patients in the 1970's in order to access the origins of their phobias and psychological issues. While hypnotizing his patients, Chamberlain began noticing that they would often regress to their birth (Chamberlain, 1988). Chamberlain collected birth memories for years and became interested in determining the veracity of his patients' birth memories, since the

mainstream belief at the time was that babies are incapable of retaining such early memories (Verny & Weintraub, 2002).

Chamberlain decided to examine the reliability of birth memories systematically. In 1986, he conducted a qualitative study in which he compared birth memories obtained by hypnosis from 10 children (ages 9 to 23) and their mothers (ages 32 to 46). The children had no conscious memories of birth, and their mothers claimed they had never shared details of the birth with their children. In this study, each pair served as its own control, and the mother's report served as a measure of reality and a standard for judging the reliability of the child's memory of birth. Participants were selected randomly for the hypnosis procedure during which interrogation was conservative and leading questions were avoided to allow participants to speak freely (Chamberlain, 1986, 1988).

When Chamberlain (1986) compared the independent narratives of each dyad, he discovered that they were coherent with each other, contained many facts that were consistent and connected, and were appropriately similar in setting, characters, and sequence. In addition, the independent narratives dovetailed at many points as if a story was told from two perspectives. Serious contradictions between narratives were rare but minor discrepancies between narratives did occur. Strikingly, children often remembered facts that were unknown to their mothers and included paranormal knowledge such as unspoken thoughts of others and details of events that occurred outside the womb before the child was born, suggesting "a sophisticated level of physical, mental and emotional consciousness at birth" (Chamberlain, 1986, p. 94), beyond anything predicted by developmental psychology at the time.

The following is an excerpt from one mother-child pair and is an example of the consistency found between mother-child narratives. The mother reports,

They sort of put her on my stomach but they're still holding onto her. I could see her...lots of blood and white stuff. She's crying. I can see the umbilical cord. My hands are fastened down because I can't reach out and touch her. I would like them to move her, wrap her up. Someone does finally take her. I'm talking to the doctors...I think they had a white cap over my hair and the nurse brings her over on my left side. But she doesn't hold her close enough so I can touch her. I really feel frustrated. I do say 'Hi!' to her. She's so cute and small and still kind of messy. Then they put her in a little warmer. I talk to the doctor about her weight.

The child says,

They put me on her stomach, sort of dumped me on her. He's talking to my mom. Everything seems to be OK and she's all right... He still seems nervous and he picked me up and gave me to somebody else. I feel bigger and heavier. I can see her but I'm not by her. Her hair is wrapped-up, like in curlers or something. She looks tired, sweaty. Nobody's talking to me. They're talking about me, I think, but not to me. They act like they know I'm there but like I don't know I'm there...The nurse kind of wiped...washed me. Then they brought me over next to my mother. She wasn't crying but something like that. She's the first one that talked to me. She said 'Hi!' Nobody else seemed to think that I was really there. Then she talked to the doctor a little bit and they took me away again.

(Chamberlain 1986, pp. 94-95)

Chamberlain's (1986) study, which was published in the *Journal of the American Academy of Medical Hypnoanalysts*, is considered a foundational study in PPN literature; it was the first study to attempt to prove clinical findings with empirical evidence and its findings are quite remarkable. However, the results of this study are preliminary. Clearly, similar studies need to be conducted on a larger sample size and by an unbiased hypnotist to strengthen the validity of Chamberlain's study. Although Chamberlain has been the only clinician to systematically examine the reliability of birth memories using hypnosis, other practitioners who used hypnotherapy have had similar findings; their clients remembered their own birth, and had recollections of out of body experiences and clairvoyant knowledge of unspoken thoughts of others during their birth (Cheek, 1986; Wambach, 1981).

Dr. William Emerson

Like Chamberlain, Psychologist William Emerson had also witnessed his clients uncover early life memories during therapy. From 1964 to 1974, Emerson conducted over 8,000 hours of intense regression sessions with adults during which prenatal and perinatal memories were accessed. Emerson used various regressive techniques with his clients, such as guided imagery, birth stimulation, and verbal regression, to name a few. The regressive work would usually be done in groups but would then be followed by individual therapy sessions. Emerson noticed pronounced and deep changes in his clients after their early traumatic experiences were uncovered, and connections and parallels between these experiences and current patterns were made. This led him to consider that by starting treatment earlier in life, adult symptoms may be prevented and that the treatment process could be completed more efficiently (Emerson 1993).

In 1974, Emerson began exploratory treatment with infants and children. In the process, he developed a somatic therapeutic approach for treating prenatal and perinatal trauma with these age groups while incorporating some of his findings from his work with adults. For example, Emerson had found that prenatal and perinatal traumas are held somatically in body postures and movements, therefore he observed for these while evaluating the infants or children he treated in order to learn about the nature of their trauma. He also found that early traumas are not only embodied but are also registered emotionally by the pre-nate to create belief systems that later influence how an individual perceives and relates to the world. Furthermore, Emerson's work with adults revealed that specific types of birth and prenatal trauma often result in certain patterns of psychological dysfunction. His goal with infants and children was to prevent these forms of psychopathologies and unfavorable belief systems from evolving (Emerson, 1989, 1993).

Emerson's work focuses on resolution of prenatal and perinatal trauma and shock. According to Emerson (1999), trauma and shock have been traditionally perceived as the same; however, his clinical work over the years has led him to believe that it is necessary to differentiate between them. He writes,

Shock refers to negative and distressing life experiences that are overwhelmingly painful, cannot be coped with and which powerfully affect the physiology and psychology of the victim. In contrast, trauma refers to negative and distressing life experiences that are emotionally painful but which can be coped with and do not surreptitiously affect the physiology and psychology of the victim. Viewed in this way, shock and trauma are both distressing experiences, but shock is the more

debilitating. Shock stems from highly stressful events in which there is little or no choice or power and in which victims feel overwhelmed. In contrast, trauma arises from events in which victims have some power to alter their course of intensity. (Emerson, 1999, p. 1)

Emerson (1999) also explains the different impact trauma and shock have on the individual,

When shock is activated, the whole shock system and all unresolved shocks are simultaneously activated, whether they are thematically related or not. This means that if one shock is restimulated, all other shocks and the entire shock system are also activated, together and at the same time. Activation occurs at unconscious levels, so that clients are not aware of simultaneous shock memories; they are only aware of distress, of dysfunctional feelings or behaviors, or of memory fragments. In contrast, activation of trauma results exclusively in restimulation of thematically related trauma, but not the entire trauma system. (p. 1)

Emerson claims that prenatals and neonates experience whatever their parents' experience and because their defensive systems are relatively immature, they are more vulnerable and unprotected from the normal distresses of life, which could be traumatizing and shocking. There is a multitude of prenatal and perinatal experiences that may leave traumatic and shocking imprints on the prenatals. These include biological and psychological crises around conception and implantation, for example conception by force or rape and unwanted pregnancies; abortion ideation or attempts; substance abuses during pregnancy; family crises during pregnancy such as separations, divorces, financial problems, violence, illness and/or death of a family member; physical and/or emotional

abuses of the pregnant woman; adoption or adoption ideations; birth interventions and complications; prematurity; prolonged separation at birth; and bonding and attachment disorders (Emerson, 1987, 1999, 2008).

The key concepts of Emerson's therapeutic approach, which was named *Somatotropic Therapy*, include regression, catharsis and integration. Through regression, the underlying traumatic experiences are uncovered. Regression usually leads to a cathartic release of unresolved emotions associated with these experiences. Once traumatic experiences are uncovered and catharted, the facilitator helps the client with the integrative process in a supportive and empathic way. Integration involves examining the connections between regressive experiences and current life patterns and belief systems. Emerson writes that as trauma is resolved "...the tenets of the old belief systems begin to shift and loosen their grip on dysfunctional facets of the personality" (Emerson, 1993, p. 5).

Typically, the therapeutic process consists of three phases and Emerson underscores the importance of pacing the process with infants and children, and letting them know that they control it. During the first phase, rapport is established with the parents and with the infant or child. This is particularly important with infants, as the underlying assumption is that they are capable of communicating. The second phase consists of a detailed observation and palpation of the infant or child's shape of face and head, which were impacted by birth pressures, as well as a body posture and movement evaluation. During the third phase of therapeutic process, one of two types of techniques is usually employed to uncover the deepest aspects of the prenatal or perinatal trauma, depending on the child's age and trauma: simulative or evocative (Emerson, 1989, 1993).

Birth-simulating massage is used for the treatment and release of birth trauma embodied within the client. It is the most frequently simulating technique, utilized in infants, children and even adults. It involves stimulating birth experiences with gentle massage on the client's cranium and shoulders on specific points, which are known to come in contact with the maternal pelvis during birth. The massage is applied while the client is positioned into his or her actual birth lie, and if birth was highly traumatic, no pressure is applied at all, rather, energetic massage is used (Emerson, 1989, 1993).

An evocative technique frequently used with infants is parent-dialoging. The parents are questioned about any traumatic events that might have occurred during the prenatal and perinatal period, such as relational upsets, death in the family and so on. The parents' feelings about these events are explored and the potential impact on the child is discussed. Then the parents are guided to make a clear distinction between their feelings and reactions and their child's feelings and reactions, and articulate these distinctions to the infant. This process on its own could be a powerful catalyst for the child to release the memory of the traumatic experience (Emerson, 1989, 1993).

Evocative techniques most frequently used with children involve games. Physical apparatus such as tunnels created by the parents' bodies are used to evoke intrauterine and birth traumas and the child is often regressed during the game. According to Emerson, it is easier for children to perceive feelings in others (or in pictures of themselves) than to recognize themselves. Therefore, children are videotaped during play and regression and are then shown the recording which focus on their faces, eyes, postures and movements. By doing so, children are able to see themselves objectively, and can recognize their feelings, often for the first time. Play therapy in the form of sand play is another

evocative technique that allows children to tell the story of their trauma in safe and clear ways using different symbolic and reality figures and objects. Other diagnostic tools employed with children include drawing, sculpting, reality play, and psychodrama (Emerson, 1987, 1989).

Although techniques are essential to the therapeutic process, Emerson reiterates that genuine empathy and compassion are the core of therapy, and are of most importance for dynamically promoting the healing process. Emerson found that while empathy is essential in older children and techniques are seldom successful without it, with younger children and infants, empathy is mandatory. Emerson also noticed how crucial the somatic intervention was in the healing process. He explains that if trauma is emotionally released thorough catharsis without the appropriate bodywork, then only a portion of the trauma is treated and resolved (Emerson, 1989, 1993).

Emerson gained a tremendous amount of experience working with infants and children. By the late 1980's he treated over 600 infants and children in birth groups and over 100 individually, and has done follow-ups of over 100 infants and children (Emerson, 1987). Over the years, he treated infants and children with a wide array of problems and symptoms: newborn "fussiness", breastfeeding and sleeping difficulties, pediatric illnesses such as bronchitis and asthma, developmental delays, temperamental behavior, behavior disorders, learning disabilities and others. Emerson contends that prenatal and birth traumas play an active role in the etiology of these problems. In regard to babies, he notes that most parents and professionals consider frequent night awakenings, crying for long periods and colic as "normal"; however, he believes these are actually the presenting symptoms of early trauma (Emerson, 1989, 1996).

In the early process of developing his treatment approach for infant and children, Emerson decided to conduct a pilot study to evaluate the effectiveness of his treatment. The study consisted of an experimental group of 15 infants and children who received treatment and a control group of 15 infants and children who had been referred to work with Emerson but eventually did not receive treatment. Emerson used a pre-treatment, post-treatment model, which assessed for changes in presenting symptoms as well as questionnaires evaluating therapeutic effectiveness. Follow up evaluations were conducted annually for 20 years (Castellino, 1995; Emerson, 1996).

Emerson found that a higher percentage of the participants in the treatment group showed changes in 10 outcome categories: resolution of presenting symptoms; resolution of somatic symptoms; prevention of potential symptoms; degree of emotional maturity; extent of mutuality and empathy; degree of self-awareness and ability to communicate; level of individuation and manifestation of unique human potential (passion and ability in unique talents and skills); and connection with the self. Some of these outcomes, namely manifestation of unique human potential, were unexpected. Another unanticipated outcome, observed only in the treatment group, was the occurrence of transpersonal experiences such as clairvoyant experiences, during or following completion of treatment (Emerson, 1993). Evidently, the pilot study was successful in confirming Emerson's preliminary hypotheses. Not only were infants and children successfully treated, but the treatment process also averaged twelve sessions, far fewer than the number of sessions required for adult treatment (Emerson, 1996).

As much as these outcomes seem impressive, Emerson's pilot study has several methodological flaws, which Emerson himself discusses in his 1996 paper *Treating Birth*

Trauma during Infancy: Dynamic Outcomes. The study's limitations include the following: The participants were self, and not randomly selected into either the control or treatment groups; the sample size was small; the results were not analyzed statistically, rather, they were reported in percentages; the treatment techniques used were being developed during the study therefore treatment methodology was inconsistent over time; Emerson was both the therapist and the researcher which could have biased the assessment process; and some of the untreated infants did receive other types of alternative treatments for their presenting symptoms, which means that the control group was contaminated to a certain extent. Emerson remarks that these limitations do not invalidate his findings but point the way toward further needed research (Contey 2006; Emerson, 1996).

The next step in empirically validating the efficacy of Emerson's treatment approach is, therefore, to design a well controlled study and carry it out on a larger sample size of children and infants. Conducting a methodologically sound study is important for two main reasons. First, it may help establish an evidence-based practice model for this therapeutic approach. Second, such a study is more likely be published in main stream psychology journals, which could make the PPN therapeutic approach more accessible and perhaps more appreciated by psychologists and psychotherapists who use traditional therapeutic techniques with their clients.

Besides pioneering a treatment approach for healing prenatal and perinatal trauma and shock in infants and newborns, Emerson has prolifically written and documented his findings in numerous publications that have become fundamental in the PPN literature: these include the books *Birth Trauma: The Psychological Effects of Obstetrical*

Interventions and Perinatal Stages Manual as well as a series of videotapes documenting treatment techniques for specific birth trauma. Emerson also started a training program for practitioners from various disciplines interested in studying and learning how to work with babies. In the late 1980's Raymond Castellino, a chiropractor, cranioacral and Polarity therapist, and Wendy Anne McCarty, a nurse and a psychotherapist, participated in Emerson's training seminar (Castellino, 1996; McCarty, 2004).

Dr. Wendy Anne McCarty

McCarty began seeing young toddlers and children in her practice in 1989, utilizing a PPN framework and what she had learned from Emerson. Like Emerson, McCarty had found that children have memories of traumatic events from their conception, prenatal, birth, and neonatal period, and that when these memories are validated, acknowledged and responded to with compassion and empathy, changes in patterns and relational dynamics would occur (McCarty, 2004).

Astounded by the disparity between western biologically based models of early development and the findings from PPN based clinical work, she sought a paradigm that would bridge the gap between the traditional models and PPN to accommodate both. More specifically, McCarty was eager to scientifically validate the clinical findings pointing to the possibility that unborn children were conscious as early as conception, a notion incompatible with the prevailing Newtonian paradigm (McCarty, 2005).

With the help of a grant from *The New Earth Foundation*, McCarty began researching. Her explorations led her to quantum physics, holographic theory, consciousness studies, and transpersonal psychology, in which she found answers to her questions. By incorporating her knowledge from these fields with the PPN perspective,

she formed an integrated model of early development. In 2004, McCarty introduced the new model in her developmental psychology book *Welcoming Consciousness: Supporting Babies Wholeness from the Beginning of Life—An Integrated Model of Early Development* (McCarty, 2002, 2004, 2005). The model will be discussed in the following chapter.

Over the years, McCarty has added a variety of healing modalities to the therapeutic techniques she utilizes for healing early trauma. Most of these come from the field of Energy Psychology and include Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT), Tapas Acupressure Techniques (TAT), and Thought Field Therapy (TFT). McCarty not only uses these techniques to treat her clients but also teaches them to parents to use at home on themselves or one their infants or children. She has found EFT to be a simple and efficient self-healing tool through which families are empowered to heal and change themselves (McCarty, 2006, 2007). McCarty's clinical case story of a 6-year-old boy with an eating phobia is an extraordinary example of how incorporating a PPN perspective with EFT in a surrogate, non-local application can heal perinatal trauma in a quick and efficient way (McCarty, 2006).

Dr. Raymond Castellino

Recognizing the potency of the prenatal and perinatal period, in 1989 Raymond Castellino resolved to dedicate the rest of his professional life to treating prenatal and perinatal trauma in babies, children and adults, and teach parents and health professionals how to welcome babies into the world so that they can reach their full potential. During the same year, Castellino began corroborating with Emerson on the prenatal and birth theory and treatment model. Bringing his perspective as an experienced body worker,

Castellino has contributed immensely to the evolution of Somatotropic Therapy (Castellino, 1995).

Castellino has integrated the Polarity paradigm with the prenatal and perinatal approach in his therapeutic work with clients. In his article *The Polarity Therapy Paradigm Regarding Pre-Conception, Prenatal and Birth Imprinting*, Castellino provides an overview of Dr. Randolph Stone's Polarity paradigm. He explores its application to the transition of a baby's consciousness and experience of pre-conception, conception, gestation and birth, and delineates the effects of trauma on the emerging being. Castellino then shows how a prenatal and perinatal approach to healing trauma in babies is consistent with Dr. Stone's energy concept, and presents a case study of a baby to illustrate how an application of the Polarity paradigm can support babies in order to heal prenatal and birth trauma (Castellino, 1995).

In 1992, Castellino began facilitating adults in exploring their early lives in a group setting he called the *Womb Surround Process Workshop*. This workshop is a more developed and refined format of the prenatal and perinatal group processes that were carried out by Lake, Grof, Reich, Orr and others during the second half of the 20th century (Castellino, n.d.; Glenn, 2002). During a four day workshop, seven participants are facilitated through group and individual work by Castellino and his trainees, to explore and re-pattern physical and emotional imprints of prenatal, birth or infancy origin. Tools used include group interactive processes, energy awareness, craniosacral work and other touch and empathy skills. Castellino has found by experience that complete and lasting transformations most often occur as a result of work in a group process (Castellino, n.d.).

In 1993, Castellino and McCarty co-founded a non-profit research clinic called *BEBA* (an abbreviation of Building and Enhancing Bonding and Attachment) in Santa Barbara, California. The purpose of the clinic was to develop and study prenatal and perinatal therapeutic work with babies and their families (McCarty, 2004). Through their work with babies and their families at BEBA, Castellino and McCarty have further refined the tools for assessing and treating prenatal and birth trauma. They have devised a set of re-patterning principles, which allow parents and professionals to facilitate the healing process in infants and children (McCarty, 2002). The re-patterning principles which allow parents and practitioners to settle, attune and be present in healing ways with babies include: Self-regulating, orienting, slowing down and attuning to bodily sensations and feelings. The re-patterning principles used by practitioners as they attend to and interact with babies and children include: Pacing to the baby's rhythm; attending to the baby's verbal and non-verbal communications; differentiating and repairing (Contey, 2006).

Scientific Basis of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

Since the early 1980's, prenatal and perinatal psychologists have been showing great interest in the various aspects of embryonic and fetal development and the impact of womb ecology on the short- and long-term health of the individual. Eager to scientifically validate the mounting clinical evidence, Thomas Verny, David Chamberlain, and others have written extensively about the development of fetal senses, fetal behavioral and emotional capacities, and the cognitive capabilities of the unborn child, such as memory and learning (Chamberlain n.d., 1988, 1990, 1994, 1999; Foster & Verny, 2007; Hepper, 1991, 2005; Thomson, 2004; Verny, 1988, 1989; Verny & Weintraub, 2002).

These scholars have drawn their work on findings from epidemiological studies, scientific research in embryology and cell biology, conscious studies, and neuroscience, as well as on direct fetal observations made possible by innovative experimental technology such as intrauterine photography and sonography (Chamberlain, 1999). The findings from these studies and observations have shattered the prevailing view of the fetus being "...dewy-eyed and unseeing, moving only reflexively and preoccupied with little beyond eating, sleeping and eliminating..." (Karr-Morse & Wiley, 1997, p. 50). In the following section I will review the scientific evidence that supports the clinical findings of PPN.

The Development of the Fetal Senses and Motion

Fascinating in its complexity, human development begins at conception. During the first 14 weeks of life, also referred to as the embryonic stage, development progresses through a sequence of layering and folding, followed by organ differentiation and limb formation. By four months, every organ system such as the heart, the liver, the gastrointestinal tract and others are largely developed and functioning (Gluckman & Hanson, 2005; Thibodeau & Patton, 1993). Notably, the nervous system, which begins to form at approximately 19 days, generates the greatest growth during the embryonic period and it is in this stage that all the structures of the brain and nervous system emerge and begin to function rudimentarily (Stables, 1999; Thomason, 2004).

Tactile. The tactile system, which is responsible for the sense of touch and pressure, is the first to develop in the womb as it emerges three weeks after conception. At eight weeks, the embryo appears to respond reflexively to touch. The embryo can sense pressure on its lips and nose at five weeks and by the ninth week - in the arms, chin

and eyelids. By 10 weeks, skin sensitivity extends to the genital area and legs, by 11 weeks to the palms and by 12 weeks to the soles. At 17 weeks, all parts of the abdomen and buttocks are sensitive and by 30 weeks, nearly every part of the body is sensitive to touch. Interestingly, the top of the head and the back remain insensitive to touch until shortly after birth, which might be nature's "way" to make the birth process less painful for the fetus (Chamberlain, n.d.; Foster & Verny, 2007). The fetus touches its face from 10 to 11 weeks post conception and contact with the umbilical cord and the uterine wall provides tactile stimulation (Hepper, 2005).

Auditory. Hearing begins during the fifth week of gestation and starts to actively function before the completion of the first trimester; however, hearing continues to slowly mature after the baby is born. By 23 weeks gestation the fetus can respond to sound and indicates sound preferences (Chamberlain, n.d.; Foster & Verny, 2007). Initially, responses are found only in the low-frequency range (250–500Hz) of adult hearing (20–20000Hz), but this range expands as the fetus matures (Hepper, 2005).

By 26 weeks, the fetus is able to learn the intonation, rhythm, and other speech patterns of the mother's voice, which is particularly powerful because it is transmitted to the womb through her own body, reaching the fetus in a stronger form than outside sounds. By 34 weeks gestation the auditory threshold levels are similar to adult preferences. This allows the fetus to develop selective preferences for specific sounds (Chamberlain, n.d.; Foster & Verny, 2007). Experience with speech sounds in the womb may begin the process of language acquisition; newborns recognize and prefer their mother's language, and are able to discriminate it from an unfamiliar language (Hepper, 2005).

Vision. The visual system begins its development during the fourth week of gestation but takes several years to mature (Thomson, 2004). Although the eyelids remain closed until about the 26th week of gestation, studies show that the fetus is sensitive to light from the 16th week; it reacts to projections of light on the maternal abdomen with heart rate accelerations as well as with the startling response (Chamberlain, n.d.; Karr-Morse & Wiley, 1997). By 32 weeks the unborn child has the same capacity to see as a newborn (Karr-Morse & Wiley, 1997), and at birth, vision is perfectly focused from 8 to 12 inches, the distance to a mother's face when feeding at the breast (Chamberlain, n.d.).

Taste. The gustatory sense is limited to the tongue, which contains the taste nerve endings. Around the eighth week after conception, taste buds begin to emerge on the tongue (Foster & Verny, 2007). Flavors from maternal diet pass into the amniotic fluid, and when the fetus begins to swallow the fluid, around the 12th week of gestation, it may taste these flavors (Hepper, 2005). Tests show that fetal swallowing increases with sweet tastes and decreases with bitter and sour tastes (Chamberlain, n.d.) and that the amniotic fluid biases the fetus for future taste preferences (Foster & Verny, 2007).

Olfactory. The early structures of the nose begin to form between six to eight weeks post conception and the olfactory sense is almost fully mature at the end of the embryonic stage. By the end of the first trimester, the main olfactory subsystem is anatomically mature and can carry out sensory performance. Modern research methods are currently unable to determine how, when and what a human fetus smells (Foster & Verny, 2007); however, newborns show a preference for their mother's odor over that of another female and have been found to orient to their own amniotic fluid. These observations are suggestive of prenatal learning of odors (Hepper, 2005).

Fetal motor development. Ultrasonic observations have revealed that the embryo begins to move at around 7 to 8 weeks after conception. These first movements are primarily reflexive and slow, originating in the spine; the back may flex or extend, and may be followed by passive movements of the arms and legs. From the 12th week of gestation, fetal activity is self-initiated and movement becomes a primary activity, sometimes spontaneous and sometimes provoked by environmental events (e.g. in response to maternal coughing or laughing). By 14 weeks, the complete repertoire of fetal movements seen throughout gestation is already evident (Chamberlain, n.d., 1999; Hepper, 2005; Thomson, 2004).

Fetal movements are essential for the formation of the joints and muscle tone. The joints initially develop with rough surfaces but as the fetus moves the joints are reshaped and develop their smooth surfaces to enable complete mobility. Malformations such as clubfoot have been linked to absence of prenatal movement in joints. Another key role of prenatal activity is to practice functions that are essential for survival after birth. For example, fetal breathing movements, which begin at about 10 weeks after conception despite the absence of air in the womb, help the neural pathways responsible for breathing to mature in order to ensure that breathing will be possible at birth (Hepper, 2005).

Fetal Behavior

This brief review of the development of the fetal senses and movement in the womb shows that the fetus is continually reacting to its environment, which is rich in tactile, auditory, visual, gustatory and olfactory stimuli. As the fetus develops, its movements become organized into periods of activity and inactivity and at the beginning

of the twenty eighth week of gestation, well defined periods of four behavioral states emerge: quiet sleep, active sleep, quiet awake, and active awake. These are actually precursors of the behavioral states seen in newborns (Hepper, 2005; Verny, 1989). Researchers have discovered that babies might be dreaming as early as 23 weeks gestation, which is when rapid eye movement during sleep is first observed (Chamberlain, n.d.).

Fetuses have been shown to exhibit various physiological reactions to an amniocentesis test done under ultrasound screening. These include increase in heart rate, loss of beat-to-beat variations in heart beat four minutes after the two minutes puncture, remaining motionless for two minutes, a decrease in breathing movements for two days, and failure to normalize these movements for four days (Chamberlain, 1994). Also associated with amniocentesis have been self-initiated self-defense maneuvers, which were observed in reaction to the needle, such as shrinking away from it or attacking it (Chamberlain, n.d.). However, Wade (1999) claims that the young fetus, which functions on a minimal cortical level, is incapable of initiating such reactions, which are merely primitive defenses.

Despite this disagreement among scholars in the field of PPN regarding the nature of the fetus' reaction to the amniocentesis test, the importance of these findings lies in the indisputable fact that unborn children do not remain idle to changes in their environment. They exhibit clear and measurable responses to this invasive test as well as to changes in their mother's physiology. For example, third trimester fetuses have been found to respond to alterations in maternal heart rate with a sharp increase in movements. In addition, ultrasound screenings of unborn children have also revealed fetal erections as

early as 16 weeks gestation. This often occurs in conjunction with finger sucking, which suggests that pleasurable self-stimulation is possible prenatally (Chamberlain, n.d.).

Whether the unborn child feels pain has been a subject of interest. Numerous lines of evidence suggest that the anatomical pathways and mechanisms for pain perception are well developed late in gestation. Observational studies of premature infants have identified pain responses around 24 to 26 weeks gestation and biochemical stress responses to needle punctures during blood transfusions have been observed as early as 23 weeks gestation. However, these are indirect measures of pain and it is still unknown whether pain is experienced subjectively by the neonate in a similar way it is experienced by older children and adults (Anand, Phil & Kickey, 1988; Chamberlain, 1999; Hepper, 2005).

Learning in Utero

Studies of newborns have demonstrated that learning abilities such as habituation, classical conditioning, and imitation are present at birth (Chamberlain, 1999; Hepper, 1991). These findings suggest that these abilities may originate in the prenatal period rather than appearing anew at birth. According to Hepper (1991), studies on fetal learning have been conducted by several researchers and can be divided into two types: studies that examine the response of the fetus to auditory stimuli in utero, and studies that examine the response of newborns to stimuli experienced before birth.

Psychologist Anthony DeCasper's studies exemplify the second type of studies Hepper (1991) mentions. In a series of studies, DeCasper (as cited in Verny, 1989) demonstrated that newborn babies recognize their mother's voice and prefer it to other women's voices. One of his studies even showed that newborns remember what they

heard in utero. He tape-recorded sixteen mothers while they each read one of two children's stories. During the last six and a half weeks of their pregnancy, each mother in the study read aloud one of these children's stories to her fetus twice a day, which by the end of pregnancy summed up to five hours of listening time to the same story. After birth, at three days of age, both recordings were played to the babies. The babies were able to switch from one recording to another by sucking on an artificial nipple. The babies heard one story if they sucked rapidly and the other story if they sucked slowly. 15 out of 16 sucked at the right rate to receive the story they had heard in utero by their mother.

An example of the first type of studies mentioned by Hepper (1991) is a study he conducted himself in which he compared two groups of 10 fetuses between 36 to 37 weeks of gestation. The study group had mothers who regularly watched a famous soap opera and the control group had mothers who did not watch the program. The soap opera's theme was used as stimulus; while the fetus was being observed using ultrasound screening, the theme was played for three minutes through headphones placed on the mother's abdomen. The number of fetal hand and leg movements was recorded and summed up during one minute before the theme was played and during the last minute of the playback. Results revealed that although there was no difference in movements between the control and study groups during the minute prior to the playback, the study group showed a significant increase in the number of movements in comparison to the control group during the last minute of the playback.

Furthermore, when this experiment was repeated using the soap opera theme played backwards, there was no significant difference in the number of movements before and after hearing the theme between groups. Hepper (1991) concluded that the

results of the second experiment support those of the first one and demonstrate that learning is specific to the tune heard in utero. In order to determine whether evidence of learning could be found before 36 to 37 weeks, the first experiment was repeated with fetuses between 29 to 30 weeks gestation. The results indicated no significant differences in the number of movements exhibited by the fetus before and after hearing the soup opera theme, suggesting that at 29 to 30 weeks gestation the fetus has not yet learned the theme (Hepper, 1991).

The apparent ability of the fetus to learn has led some to believe that development can be enhanced through programs of prenatal stimulation (Contey, 2006; Hepper, 2005). The Prenatal University was the first stimulation program ever to be designed and tested. Developed by obstetrician Rene Van de Carr, the program, beginning at twenty weeks gestation, included two five-minute daily sessions during which mother or father practiced stimulating their prenaté's auditory, tactile and spatial senses through a series of interactive exercises, which progressively got more complex over time (Van de Carr & Lehrer, 1988).

Van de Carr & Lehrer (1986) systematically studied the Prenatal University program. The study compared three groups of 50 participants each: a group of full participants, a group of partial participants and a group of non-participants. This study revealed a significant difference in favor of the families who fully participated in the program in early speech, physical growth, bonding and successful breastfeeding. Although these findings seem impressive, their reliability are questioned as the information regarding the babies' achievements was based on parents' self report.

Van de Carr's work inspired researchers internationally. Various stimulation programs were developed and tested systematically in Thailand, Venezuela and Spain, all of which generally showed that enriched babies display superior fine and gross motor skills, earlier speech and language development, earlier smiling and greater contentment after birth, superior visual and auditory perception, coordination, and cognitive development (Chamberlain, 1997; Contey, 2006).

Despite these apparent advantages, structured prenatal stimulation programs have been criticized. Uplinger and Axness (1999) caution that stimulation programs might disturb an ongoing process of growth taking place "perfectly well in fetal development" (p.1). They express their concern about the possible inherent message in such programs being one of dissatisfaction with the baby's performance and claim these programs portray the modern cultural embrace of anything bearing the label "educational". Uplinger and Axness believe that it is through empowering the mother to be "the best most authentic self" and love herself and the baby, that an unborn child's intelligence is fostered (p. 1).

The Development of Memory and Consciousness

The profusion of evidence of birth memories and gestational memories going back to conception and even before, found in clinical and experimental research, has challenged two premises regarding human memory in traditional psychology; the first is that our ability to retain memories begins at the age of three, and the second is that memory is confined to brain matter. Recent research suggests that our ability to remember may not be dependent on the brain and/or the central nervous system (CNS) (Chamberlain, 1990; Verny & Weintraub, 2002). In her groundbreaking article, *Two*

Voices from the Womb: Evidence for Physically Transcendent and a Cellular Source of Fetal Consciousness, transpersonal psychology researcher and theorist, Jenny Wade (1999), presents the three current major theories of memory and examines PPN findings of early memory and consciousness through the lens of each theory.

According to Wade (1999), there are currently three schools of memory theories that are grouped by the location of memory in the body: local, non-local, and completely non-physical, or transcendent. Although each of these schools is supported by empirical data, none of it is conclusive. In the local theory of memory, and consistent with Western medical tradition, identifiable brain structures store memory, suggesting that memory and consciousness are dependent only on the CNS. Therefore, technically, this school of memory can only account for prenatal memories when some memory structures in the brain begin to function during the third trimester.

There are several non-local memory models. In general, non-local memory models explain how memories may be stored in identifiable cellular structures such as RNA or hormones, rather than in the CNS (Wade, 1999). Verny (as cited in Wade, 1999) gives an account of how early experiences in the womb may be stored on a cellular level: the unborn child is exposed to hormonal imbalances caused by maternal emotional upset, during which a maternal mnemonic hormone called ACTH is released. The baby becomes flooded with ACTH, which enhances the retention of these negative experiences on a cellular level. When the number of these moments and memories reaches a critical level and as memory structures begin to form within the CNS during the third trimester, the baby begins to react in rudimentary emotional and physical patterns and begins to form an underdeveloped sense of self, distinct from the mother.

Both local and non-local memory models can, therefore, account only for reported memories of events that have taken place late in pregnancy when the brain and nervous system are fairly developed. However, they are unable to explain complex cognitive recollections of events surrounding conception and pregnancy, especially those taking place outside the mother's body (Wade, 1999). Wade (1999) asserts that only the non-physical memory model can explain the extraordinary memories mentioned above. This model suggests that early memories are not stored within the CNS or within other cells of the body; rather, a transcendent self, that exists parallel to the physical self, records them. The transcendent self is conscious, fully mature and insightful and can explain a much more advanced state of prenatal ego development

Contey (2006), who cites the writing of Jenny Wade and physicist David Bohm, notes that the non-physical memory model has emerged from a post-Newtonian paradigm, called the holonomic paradigm. The word holonomic means "the law of wholeness" (Wade, 1996, p. 8). Born from twentieth century discoveries in fields such as quantum physics, field theory and holography, the holonomic perspective offers a new view of reality. Where the Newtonian paradigm views the world as mechanistic and materialistic, one that could be experienced only through the senses, the holonomic paradigm acknowledges a second order of reality, which transcends the physical reality and consists of pure, infinite and absolute energy. Bohm (as cited in Contey, 2006) called this second order the *implicate* order, and the physical order of reality the *explicate* order. He believed that the explicate order derives from the much larger implicate order.

Wade (as cited in Contey, 2006) explains that when we look at a human being through the lens of the holonomic paradigm the explicate order is the physical body,

which could be sensed and measured. The implicate order is associated with the physically transcendent source of mind or consciousness, which she refers to as our “spiritual nature”. McCarty's integrated model of early human development builds heavily on the holonomic paradigm and the ideas put forth by Bohm and Wade. It recognizes a dual perspective of awareness from conception on. The transcendent and human perspectives together form what McCarty calls the *Integrated Self*, which is extremely sensitive and receptive:

Through our transcendent perspective, we have omni-awareness of our parents and others' thoughts, feelings, and intentions that arise from their conscious and subconscious mind: Through our human self, our experience is intricately related to our mother's experience, the health of our womb, and physical/emotional journey at birth. Based on these early conditions we form a foundational holographic blueprint for life. This blueprint becomes the infrastructure from which we grow and experience life at every level of our being—physical, emotional, mental, relational, and spiritual. Our early experiences become part of our implicit memory reflected in our subconscious and in our autonomic functioning. These affect us below the level of our conscious awareness and directly shape our very perceptions and conceptions of “reality”. (McCarty, 2005, p. 19)

McCarty's integrated model of early development challenges our traditional understanding of babies and human development, and reaches far beyond what other developmental theories have previously offered (Contey, 2006). It has greatly informed the major principles of PPN.

Applications of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

Prenatal Health

One of the focal interests of the field of PPN has been the health of the unborn child and the promotion of optimal fetal development. Of central importance to the discussion of prenatal health is the resolution of the long lasting debate regarding the role nature and nurture play in human development. Until the 1950's, the development of the human fetus was believed to be completely predetermined in an unalterable way by its genes (Karr-Morse & Wiley, 1997; Nathanielsz & Vaughan, 2001). An extensive body of literature that came out during that period, which documented that fetuses could be harmed by a variety of events experienced by their mothers, such as malnutrition and exposure to x-rays, medications, and certain chemicals (Steingraber, 2001) refuted this belief.

It was only in the early 1970's that researchers who studied prenatal development began investigating the importance of environmental experience in initiating and channeling development (Broderick & Blewitt, 2006). Since then, molecular biologists have generally accepted the fact that environment affects gene expression in the womb, and it is now well established that nature and nurture overlap in the process of prenatal development (Broderick & Blewitt, 2006; Gluckman & Hanson, 2005; Lipton, 1998; Nathanielsz & Vaughan, 2001; Odent, 2006). Thomson (2004) points out that as early as 14 days after conception, with the implantation of the placenta and the formation of the umbilical cord, the mother and her environment influence gene expression in the developing embryo.

Over the past decades, evidence from human epidemiological data, and research with humans and animal studies, have shown that life before birth strongly influences our health for life (Gluckman, Hanson, Cooper & Thornburg, 2008; Nathanielsz & Vaughan, 2001). Originated by David Barker, programming theory, which accentuates the impact of maternal environment on prenatal development, explains the fetal origins of adult disease. It suggests that an event occurring during a sensitive period of fetal development causes long-term changes in the structure and function of important organs. These changes have implications for later health such as a susceptibility to develop chronic disease (Nathanielsz & Vaughan, 2001; Rice, Jones, & Thapar, 2007).

Nathanielsz and Vaughn (2001) explain that the fetus responds to oxygen and nutritional shortages by diverting resources to the brain, which compromises the development of other tissues and organs and their function later on in life. For example, inadequate growth of the liver could result in higher cholesterol later in life since the liver is central in regulating cholesterol, and a smaller pancreas could lead to adult onset diabetes. Through maternal environment, which is mediated by the placenta, the fetus “learns” about the world outside the womb and “prepares” itself for this perceived environment. Therefore, a baby who was malnourished during intrauterine life may not be able to cope with an environment plentiful and rich in food afterwards, and will have a greater likelihood of becoming obese.

The implications of this information in terms of public health is that the health and well being of pregnant women should be seen as top priority, and that preventative measures such as the education of young people in relation to their responsibilities during pregnancy are implemented (Gluckman et al., 2008; Odent, 2006). Nathanielsz and

Vaughn (2001), recommend that pregnant women should strive to create an optimal environment for their unborn child and discuss several factors that influence pregnancy. These factors will be briefly discussed next.

Nutrition during pregnancy. Nathanielsz and Vaughn (2001) claim that the mother's nutritional status during pregnancy is the single most important factor in baby's growth but also stress the importance of the mother's nutritional status prior to conception. In addition, they underscore the programming effect of the kind of food the baby gets before birth; it can affect the baby's life-long weight, blood pressure, blood sugar profile and cardiovascular health. The 2008 American Dietetic Association's position statement named *Nutrition and lifestyle for a healthy pregnancy outcome* (Kaiser & Allen, 2008) echoes Nathanielsz and Vaughn's assertions: "Women need to attain good nutritional status before, during, and after pregnancy to optimize maternal health and reduce the risk of pregnancy complications, birth defects, and chronic disease in their children in later adulthood" (p. 554). Among the important key points presented in this position statement are guidelines regarding appropriate weight gain during pregnancy, recommendations for food and fluid intake, and guidance on vitamin supplementation.

Smoking during pregnancy. Smoking has been totally discouraged during pregnancy in recent years due to the wealth of data on the dangers of tobacco to the fetus (Nathanielsz & Vaughan, 2001). Maternal smoking during pregnancy reduces placental blood flow and increases blood concentration of carbon monoxide, both of which limit the oxygen and nutrients supplied to the fetus, which may lead to intrauterine growth retardation. Furthermore, nicotine adversely affects the fetus' developing nervous system causing neuronal damage, which may imply neurobehavioral and cognitive effects.

Because concentrations of nicotine on the fetal side of the placenta generally reach levels fifteen percent higher than maternal levels, even low levels of cigarette smoking may expose the fetus to harmful amounts of nicotine (Law, Stroud, LaGasse, Niaura, Liu, & Lester, 2008).

Pregnancy and birth outcomes that have been associated with maternal smoking during pregnancy are increase rates of spontaneous abortion, stillbirth, sudden infant death syndrome, clef palate, preterm birth and low birth weight. Offspring behavioral abnormalities have also been associated with maternal smoking during pregnancy. These include increased evidence of attentional deficits, impaired learning and memory, lowered IQ, cognitive dysfunction, later childhood conduct problems, substance use, and early adult criminality. However, the causal effect between maternal smoking during pregnancy and these behavioral outcomes is questioned due to the existing literature's inability to separate prenatal exposure effects from possible confounding environmental and genetic factors (Knopik, 2009).

Alcohol consumption during pregnancy. Alcohol crosses the placenta and the fetus' blood-brain barrier rapidly and easily, and can affect the development of the fetal nervous system by interfering with cell migration, neurotransmitter production, and brain growth (Karr-Morse & Wiley, 1997). The full spectrum of birth defects caused by prenatal alcohol exposure is referred to as fetal alcohol spectrum disorders (FASD) and may include mild and subtle changes, such as slight learning disabilities and/or physical abnormalities. Fetal alcohol syndrome (FAS), which falls under this spectrum, is the most serious consequence of maternal drinking during pregnancy and is related to a heavy intake of alcohol. It is characterized by growth deficiency manifested by small overall

height and small head size, CNS disorders, including mental retardation, and a distinctive pattern of abnormal facial features (Huizink & Mulder, 2006; Jacobson & Jacobson, 2002; Office of the Surgeon General, 2005).

Prenatal exposure to low to heavy alcohol levels has been associated with neurobehavioral and cognitive deficits in the human offspring, including attention deficits, hyperactivity, and high distractibility (Huizink & Mulder, 2006; Karr-Morse & Wiley, 1997). Gray, Mukherjee and Rutter (2009), argue that unlike studies on the impact of heavy prenatal drinking, those done on low-to-moderate levels and binge drinking suffer from methodological issues, such as difficulty in measuring alcohol consumption accurately from self-report and the presence of confounding factors, and stress the need for confirmation from stronger research designs. Nevertheless, the Office of the Surgeon General (2005) has declared that no amount of alcohol consumption can be considered safe during pregnancy and has recommended that pregnant women and those who may become pregnant should abstain from alcohol consumption.

Physical activity and exercise during pregnancy. Attitudes towards exercise during pregnancy have changed dramatically over that past 50 years. Until the mid 1980's, the medical establishment took a very conservative position on the subject of maternal exercise during pregnancy and was generally opposed to it, until scientific research on animals followed by human studies began to demonstrate the benefits of exercising during pregnancy (Nathanielsz & Vaughan, 2001; Moris & Johnson, 2005). In 2002, the American College of Obstetrics and Gynecologists (ACOG) published a position statement recommending 30 minutes or more of moderate exercise on most, if

not at all, days of the week for pregnant women in the absence of either medical or obstetric complications (ACOG, 2002).

Gavard and Artel (2008) have critically reviewed all available existing studies on the effects of exercise before or during pregnancy. They have concluded that despite methodological pitfalls in the studies published, the evidence suggest that exercise is beneficial during pregnancy; it could prevent and limit adverse maternal and fetal morbidities and mortalities and provide a long-term benefit through reduction of maternal weight gain during pregnancy, and improvements in cardiovascular fitness. In addition, the authors state that the literature does not report any links between maternal exercise and adverse fetal outcomes. They conclude with a call for randomized controlled trials to further clarify the protective effect of different types, frequencies, and intensities of exercise on maternal and fetal outcomes.

Prenatal Parenting

In Western society, parenting has been traditionally and pervasively viewed to begin after birth. However, PPN discoveries regarding the dynamic circumstances of life before birth and the unborn child's capacities and capabilities have challenged this notion and have set in motion a paradigm shift in parenting, within which parenting is viewed to begin at conception (Chamberlain, 1997; Verny, 1988; Verny & Weintraub, 2002).

Although formal and specific guidelines for prenatal parenting or parenting from conception to birth are currently missing (Chamberlain, 2003), several scholars in the field of PPN have emphasized the importance of prospective parents becoming aware of the consciousness and abilities of their unborn babies and encourage parents to learn to

interact and communicate with their babies during pregnancy (Barrack, 2007; Chamberlain 2003; McCarty, 2008; Riley, 1988).

When parents understand the potential impact their state of being has on their unborn babies, they are better able to acknowledge their babies' experience and take measures to mitigate it in times when mother or father are experiencing personal or relational difficulties. For example, McCarty (2008) recommends that when a mother is having a difficult experience or stressful reaction, she should include her baby by communicating and saying something like: "I'm feeling so stressed today and angry. I know you are experiencing this too. I'm sorry. I know that doesn't feel good. I'm going to deal with it so we can both feel better soon" (P. 2). Scholars in the field of PPN (McCarty, 2007; Verny & Weintraub, 2002) recommend decreasing stress during pregnancy, as stress has been found to have numerous deleterious effects on the baby.

The effects of prenatal maternal stress. Prenatal maternal stress (PMS) has been shown to have short-term effects on birth and on the prenatate, as well as long-term developmental, emotional and behavioral effects that extend into infancy and childhood. Among pregnancy and birth outcomes, PMS has been consistently associated with low birth weight and preterm labor and has also been shown to be a risk factor for smaller head circumference in the baby, which is considered a measure of brain development (Lazinski et al., 2008; Mulder, Robles, Huizink, Van den Bergh, Buitelaar & Visser, 2002).

Smaller head circumference, low birth weight and prematurity have all been associated with an increased risk for several negative developmental outcomes such as decreased academic ability, poorer cognitive ability, lower IQ scores, behavioral

problems, psychological distress and major depressive disorder. Children who were born with low birth weight have been shown to be at a higher risk for hyperactivity and have difficulties in interacting with peers (Lazinski et al., 2008).

Among long-term developmental effects that have been associated with PMS are delayed motor and mental development (Huizink, de Medina, Mulder, Visser & Buitelaar, 2003) and poorer language abilities (Laplante, Barr & Brunet, 2004). Emotional and behavioral outcomes that have been associated with PMS include attention regulation difficulties (Huizink, de Medina, Mulder, Visser & Buitelaar, 2002) and “difficult” temperament (Gutteling et al., 2005; Huizink et al., 2003).

Much of our understanding of the mechanism by which maternal stress is transmitted to the baby comes from animal models (Lazinski et al., 2008). Transplacental transport of maternal stress hormones to the fetus is one of the mechanisms that have been suggested to explain the link between PMS and negative outcomes in the offspring (Mulder et al., 2002). It is theorized that maternal stress hormones that cross the placenta may have a programming effect on the prenatate as well as on the placenta itself. Animal studies suggest that elevated maternal stress hormones affect the fetus’ hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, which plays a key role in the body’s stress response, resulting in an altered and overactive stress response system in adult life (Nathanielsz, 1999; Nathanielsz & Vaughan, 2001). Furthermore, animal and human studies now suggest that elevated maternal stress hormones during the first trimester may cause preterm labor by priming hormonal changes in the placenta (Challis, 1995; Sandman et al., 2006).

In his book *Prenatal Parenting* neonatologist Frederick Wirth (2001) claims that when a pregnant mother becomes stressed, the fact that she is stressed is not as important as how quickly and how well she is able to manage the stress and reduce the stress hormones in her body. When a mother is able to recognize she is stressed and uses techniques to reduce the hormone surge and keep the hormone system in balance, the baby's brain is "bathed" with comforting hormones. This teaches both brains that stress is okay, because there is recovery from it. Wirth (2001) as well as Nathanielsz and Vaughan (2001) underscore the importance of reducing maternal stress during pregnancy. They recommend techniques such as exercise, progressive relaxation, meditation and yoga to help decrease PMS.

Shifting back to the concept of prenatal parenting, another emerging theme in the PPN literature that is pertinent to the process of parenting during the prenatal period is becoming aware of our childhood and our relationships with our parents and resolving any remaining conflicts and issues, so that we do not pass on unhealthy patterns from our own past to our children (McCarty & Glenn, 2008; Verny & Weintraub, 2002). O'Leary (1992), who writes about the parenting process in the prenatal period, claims that a major psychological impact of pregnancy involves the "awakening of unconscious, preverbal issues stemming from the parent's own experience of infancy and toddlerhood. These issues relate to how an individual was nurtured by his/her own parent" (pp.113-114). According to O'Leary, as pregnancy unfolds people begin to reflect on how they were parented and think about how they may want to parent the child they are about to have, but inevitably, parents' psychological well-being will influence how they function as parents.

Attachment theory and parenting. In their book *Parenting From the Inside Out*, child psychiatrist Daniel Siegel and early child and parent educator Mary Hartzell write about how parents can become aware of how their childhood experiences, particularly issues related to early attachment, have impacted their lives and influence their parenting. Building on attachment theory and research in affective neuroscience, Siegel and Hartzell (2003) make a point that making sense of one's childhood experiences can help a parent build a more effective and enjoyable relationship with his or her child.

Attachment theory, originated by British psychiatrist and psychoanalyst John Bowlby in the late 1950's, maintains that the actual experiences that children have with their parents play an important role in providing them with an internal sense of well-being that is called a "secure base" (Siegel and Hartzell, 2003). According to Bowlby (1982) "A young child's experience of an encouraging, supportive and cooperative mother, and a little later father, gives him a sense of worth, a belief in the helpfulness of others, and a favorable model on which to build future relationships" (p. 378). Mary Ainsworth, a Canadian research psychologists who worked with Bowlby, developed a laboratory-based procedure called the *Strange Situation* to test Bowlby's theory. By observing and assessing one-year-olds and their caregivers in a series of separation and reunion episodes including encounters with a stranger, Ainsworth discovered three types of attachment styles she categorized as secure, insecure avoidant, and insecure anxious/ambivalent (Siegel and Hartzell, 2003).

The majority of infants fall into the category of securely attached. These infants may be upset during separation, but seek proximity and are quickly soothed by the parent at the reunion. Avoidantly attached infants do not express any signs of distress upon the

parent's departure and either avoid or turn away from the parent at reunion, but measurement of their physiological stress response reveals that they actually do notice the parent's return. Anxiously attached infants seek proximity with the parents upon return but are not easily soothed; they cry and reach to be held but then attempt to leave once picked up (Main, 2000). A fourth category of infant attachment, disorganized attachment, was added later by Mary Main, Ainsworth's student, and her colleagues. Disorganized infants exhibit chaotic and disorienting behavior during reunion with the parent (Hesse & Main 2000; Siegel and Hartzell, 2003).

Ainsworth found that the quality of the parent-child relationship during the first year of life produces a specific type of attachment style in the infant. In general, parents who are sensitive to their child's signals have securely attached infants; parents who are neglectful or rejecting tend to have avoidently attached infants; and parents who are inconsistently available and may behave intrusively have anxiously attached infants. Later on, Main found that parents who exhibit frightening behaviors toward their children tend to have disorganized attached infants (Siegel and Hartzell, 2003).

To better understand why parents of children with different attachment styles act in such ways, Main and her colleagues developed the *Adult Attachment Interview (AAI)*, a series of twenty questions about childhood and relationships, through which the parents' attachment style is assessed. The analysis of the interview focused on *how* the adult's story is told rather than if the story happened the way it is described. The way in which the adult has made sense of his or her life is reflected in the degree to which the memories have been integrated into a coherent narrative. Following interview analysis, the adult is classified into one of four attachment categories. Research using the AAI has

shown that the AAI classification is highly predictive of a child's type of attachment to the parent; a more coherent parental narrative predicts a more secure attachment of that parent's child. In other words, a parent's own early experiences of being cared for has a direct impact, and strongly predicts how he or she will parent their own children (Contey, 2006; Siegel and Hartzell, 2003).

In *Parenting From the Inside Out*, Siegel and Hartzell (2003) guide their readers through the process of developing a coherent narrative of their past. The importance of doing so lies in the scientifically proven fact brought forth by the authors that when unresolved early trauma unconsciously persists, parents are more inclined to react inappropriately when their children do something to stir-up the unconscious memories of bothersome early experiences. When parents become conscious of these early traumatic experiences, they are provided "an opportunity for reflection, acknowledgement, understanding, healing and ultimately new ways to support and connect with their children" (Contey, 2006, p. 61).

Community Project

Rationale

The emerging field of PPN has given us a new understanding of babies and has challenged our assumptions regarding early human development. Findings from PPN oriented clinical work with infants, children and adults have consistently pointed to the possibility that unborn children and infants are conscious, aware and are able to remember, and to the likelihood of a strong association between prenatal and perinatal experiences and persisting belief systems and behavioral patterns.

Scholars in the field of PPN have integrated findings from numerous fields of scientific study and direct fetal observations to show that the human fetus is sensing, learning, and reacting to the environment. The intrauterine environment, which is predominantly shaped by the mother's physical and emotional state, is now understood to affect gene expression in the process of fetal development. PPN scholars therefore advocate the promotion of maternal physical and psychological well being during pregnancy, through optimal nutritional intake, healthy lifestyle, and stress reduction, as well as prenatal communication and bonding with the baby.

Although discoveries in PPN have direct implications for parenting, pregnancy, birthing practices, and psychotherapy, and should concern anyone who has a role in bringing babies into the world and raising children, they have mostly remained ignored by mainstream psychology and are largely unavailable to the public (Adzema, 2004). To date, most of the information about PPN is written in English, and is available in professional journals, several books and a small number of internet websites. As a result, people in non-English speaking countries have limited access to the important discoveries of PPN. Israel, in which the spoken language is Hebrew, is one of these countries. In order to make the information about PPN available to the Israeli public, it is necessary to translate it into Hebrew and publicize it.

Furthermore, making information about PPN available to the Israeli public appears to be crucial in light of the currently held perceptions of pregnancy and birth among this population, particularly Israeli women. Tzipi Ivry, an Israeli social anthropologist, has studied Israeli women's perception of pregnancy in the turn of the 21st century. Ivry (2004) found that Israeli pregnant women are constantly haunted by fears of

fetal abnormalities and are therefore preoccupied with collecting medical information about inborn abnormalities and their prenatal detection. Ivry reports a growing tendency of young Israeli women with low-risk pregnancies and with no prior indication of any fetal problem to undergo intensive prenatal testing, including amniocentesis. According to Ivry, Israeli women also tend to terminate pregnancies following the diagnosis of relatively minor defects such as cleft lip and deformed feet in significantly higher numbers than their counterparts in Europe and the USA.

Ivry (2004) found that genetic explanations for fetal abnormalities loom large in the Israeli theory of gestation, which according to Ivry, inevitably makes it a fatalistic theory in nature; if the unborn child's health is completely determined by his or her genetic makeup, there is not much one can do to influence fetal health. During her research, Ivry also discovered that carrying the burden of constantly worrying for the well being of their unborn baby is a great source of emotional stress for Israeli pregnant women. To overcome their fears, Ivry says, women adapt emotional strategies of detachment from their fetuses, especially during the first half of pregnancy, and often even later. These strategies create "a conceptual and practical division between the process of pregnancy and the fetus" (p. 344) and the practical meaning of this is that Israeli women approach the idea of prenatal bonding very hesitantly; "the 'fetus' remains an ambiguous being that is more like a 'suspect'" (p. x).

The prevailing Israeli view of the fetus' destiny being genetically predetermined, the emotional stress which is evidently common among Israeli pregnant women, and the hesitance with which they tend to approach prenatal bonding, all make the new discoveries in PPN relevant to Israeli women more than ever. Moreover, a quick glance at

statistical data on Israeli reproduction and birth practices further consolidates the need for introducing PPN discoveries and principles to the Israeli public. Birth rates have been steadily rising in Israel in the past 30 years and have reached their highest rate in 2007, when 151, 679 babies were born - almost double the birth rate in 1970 (Ezra, 2008). Israel also has one of the highest total fertility rates among developed countries with a rate of 2.9 babies per woman in the year of 2007 (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2008; United Nations, 2008)

Reproduction in Israel is highly medicalized (Ivry & Teman, 2008). This is reflected in a flourishing industry of prenatal testing (Ivry, 2004) and in the government subsidization of conceptive technologies, which has led Israel to have the highest rate of IVF fertility clinics per capita in the world (Ivry & Teman, 2008). 99% of Israeli women give birth in the hospital (Ivry, 2004) and the use of birth interventions is quite high. For example, in 2007, 50.2% of women elected to use epidural anesthesia during their birth, and 19.2% of the women delivered their babies via caesarean section (Ezra, 2008). The high percentage of birth interventions reflects the Israeli perception of childbirth. According to Leisner (as cited in Shuval-Cohen, 2008) the Israeli public perceives birth as a dangerous affair, and believes medicine and science should therefore support the process. From a PPN perspective, birth interventions are the leading cause of emotional birth trauma (Emerson, 1997), and scholars in the field of PPN believe birth interventions should be avoided unless they are medically necessary (McCarty & Glenn, 2008; Verny & Weintraub, 2002).

Description

Due to current perceptions of pregnancy and birth among Israelis, and in light of the fact that most of the information about PPN has been published in English, it is essential to expose the Israeli population to the new discoveries of PPN by translating them into Hebrew. One of the most common and practical ways to disseminate information to the public nowadays is through the internet. Therefore the chosen community project is a Hebrew website about PPN. The goal of the website is to provide information about PPN to an Israeli audience of lay people, particularly prospective parents and their families. The website is also meant to facilitate discussion about the emerging field of PPN among the Israeli psychology milieu and obstetric health care providers.

The process of building the website included several stages. The first stage consisted of defining the target audience, deciding what material would be included and forming an outline of the desired website. Next, a market survey of potential Israeli companies that design and build websites was conducted and among the companies that were considered, Kika Studio (<http://www.kika-studio.com>) was chosen. Once a company was chosen, the website and its design were discussed and decided upon, and a time frame for completion was set. At this point the name of the website and the Uniform Resource Locator (URL) or web address were chosen.

The next stage was to translate the information from the academically written literature review into Hebrew, in a web-appropriate language. This stage was the most time consuming and challenging and required some understanding of how to present information on the internet so that the reader is compelled to continue reading the

content. Once the website was designed and built, the content was uploaded and the website was launched. Finally, the new website was advertised through two popular Israeli pregnancy and childbirth related websites (www.leida.co.il and www.leyda.org.il), a well known Israeli website about psychology (www.hebpsy.net), the Israeli midwives association website (www.midwives.co.il), and through Google search engine's advertising program – *Google Adwords*.

The website is called "Prenatal and perinatal psychology" and the site's URL is www.ppn-info.net. The main navigation bar includes seven categories: "Introduction to PPN", "Information for parents", "Information for professionals", "Research", "Resources", "About", and "Contact". The website home page (see appendix A) includes the main navigation bar, a welcome message, a search engine, and a news window for advertising upcoming events, new published articles, etc. Some of the seven main categories include subcategories. When a surfer clicks on each category on the main navigation bar, a subcategory list will appear in a box on the left hand side of the page, to make each subcategory accessible.

The category "Introduction to PPN" (see appendix B) includes four subcategories:

1. "Definition of PPN" (see appendix C) gives a broad definition of prenatal and perinatal psychology.
2. "History of PPN" (see appendix D) highlights the early and more recent history of the field.
3. "Pioneers of the field" (see appendix E) presents each of the following pioneers: Thomas Verny, David Chamberlain, William Emerson, Raymond Castellino, and

Wendy Anne McCarty, their photos, a brief description of their work and contribution, and a link to their website.

4. "12 guiding principles" (see appendix F) presents McCarty and Glenn's 12 guiding principles of PPN.

The "Information for Parents" category (see appendix G) includes three subcategories:

1. "Factors that influence pregnancy" (see appendix H) presents information on the following five topics: prenatal maternal stress, nutrition during pregnancy, smoking during pregnancy, prenatal alcohol consumption and physical activity and exercise during pregnancy.
2. "Your amazing unborn child" (See appendix I) discusses the development of the fetal senses and motion, fetal behavior, learning in utero and the development of memory and consciousness.
3. "Classes and workshops" (See appendix J) includes upcoming PPN related classes and workshops for prospective parents.

The category "Information for professionals" (see appendix K) includes one subcategory named "Workshops and conferences" (see appendix L), which contains information about upcoming PPN related professional workshops and conferences. "Articles" (see appendix M) is a special application for adding research summaries and classifying them by topic.

The "Resources" category (see appendix N) consists of five subcategories:

1. "Professionals' directory" (see appendix O) presents a preliminary list of professionals who work in the field of PPN.
2. "Books" (see appendix P) lists recommended books about PPN.

3. "Journals" (see appendix Q) lists recommended journals in the field of PPN.
4. "Websites" (see appendix R) lists recommended websites about PPN.
5. "Continuing education" (see appendix S) lists universities that offer graduate degrees in PPN.

"About" (see appendix T), introduces me as the initiator and creator of the website and contains biographic information as well as a link to my Curriculum Vitae. And "Contact" (see appendix U) enables surfers to contact me via e-mail or through an online contact form.

The first Hebrew website about PPN is a work in progress. The next step is to add new applications and content to the website. Future plans include adding information about preconception health and how to physically and emotionally prepare for pregnancy, and information about preterm labor and how it may be avoided, under "Information for parents." Two other important topics to include under this category are "The implications of birth interventions" and "Birth and bonding." Other plans are to summarize and translate PPN related articles and studies and upload them to the website under the "Research" category, using the existing article-editor application.

The current website permits limited interaction with the targeted audience. Adding a forum application can solve this problem and enhance communication options between myself and the site visitors, as well as communication among the visitors themselves. Two forums are planned; under "Information for professionals", a password protected forum will be added in order to facilitate discrete discussion between professionals about PPN related experience such as case reports and clinical findings, and an open forum (not password protected), intended for the general public, will be added

under "Information for parents", so that lay people could ask questions about PPN, and share their thoughts and personal stories.

Since PPN is practically unknown to the Israeli public, the main emphasis during the preliminary stage of the website design was to provide a definition of PPN, how it has evolved, who the major pioneers of the field are, and the major findings and principles of the field. This information is pertinent to the targeted website audiences: prospective parents and professionals, and is therefore situated under "Introduction to PPN" - the first category listed on the main navigation bar. The emphasis during the next stage of the website development will be on expanding its content, and creating a forum application that will facilitate and enhance communication among site visitors. The needs of each audience will be more specifically addressed during this stage by creating a separate forum for each, and by presenting information in two forms: research summaries written in an academic style aimed more for professionals, and content written in simple language aimed for the lay person. However, access to both types of information will be open to both audiences.

The intention of the new website is to provide Israeli prospective parents and professionals in the field of psychology and obstetrics access to the new discoveries of PPN in the Hebrew language. My hope is that exposing these audiences to the findings and principals of PPN will transform the way in which they perceive unborn babies and infants and promote a shift in Israeli women's currently held perceptions of pregnancy and birth. I believe that when mothers understand the sentient nature of their unborn babies and the important role womb ecology plays in their babies' future physical health and emotional well-being, they may become more inclined to communicate and bond

with them during the prenatal period, seek ways to promote their own mental health while pregnant, and be more conscientious of their choices during childbirth.

Summary and Conclusions

PPN has been evolving as a psychotherapeutic approach since the early 1900's and as an interdisciplinary field of study for the past 30 years. Although a relatively "new" field, PPN has yielded numerous discoveries that have challenged our understanding of early human development, and have profound implications for psychotherapy, pregnancy, birthing practices, and parenting. These discoveries have primarily stemmed from clinical work with clients of various ages, as well as from scientific research.

PPN oriented clinical work with babies, children and adults have consistently pointed to the likelihood of a strong association between prenatal and perinatal experiences and persisting belief systems and behavioral patterns, and to the possibility that unborn children and infants are conscious, aware and able to remember. Science however, is just beginning to support the idea that consciousness and memory are possible as early as conception and perhaps even before. Nevertheless, clinicians in the field of PPN have developed innovative therapeutic techniques for resolving prenatal and perinatal trauma, and have devised a set of guiding principles for welcoming and caring for babies so that such wounding could be prevented from happening in the first place.

Scholars in the field of PPN have integrated findings from epidemiological studies, cell biology, biomedical research, embryology and direct fetal observations, to show that the human fetus is sensing, learning, and reacting to the environment, and that life in the womb strongly influences our health for life. It is now well established that the

intrauterine environment, which is predominantly shaped by the mother's physical and emotional state, affects gene expression in the process of fetal development, and that maternal stress during pregnancy has deleterious effects on the offspring.

Based on these findings, scholars in the field of PPN advocate the promotion of maternal physical and psychological well being during pregnancy, through optimal nutritional intake, healthy lifestyle, and stress reduction, as well as prenatal communication and bonding with the baby. Furthermore, building on findings from affective neuroscience and attachment studies on parenting, scholars in the field also underscore the importance of resolving any childhood relational issues and conflicts, as a way for parents to avoid passing on unhealthy patterns from their past to their children.

PPN carries a great potential of transforming the world because it has given us a new perspective of unborn children and infants and has offered us new ways of welcoming and being with babies. Scholars in the field of PPN should make every effort to disseminate their new discoveries among anyone who has a role in bringing babies into the world and raising children. Concomitantly, clinicians in the field of PPN should strive to empirically validate the specificity and efficacy of their treatment modalities using evidence-based research methods. By doing so, they will be bringing their new therapeutic approach a step higher towards being recognized and accepted by mainstream psychology.

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Appendices

Appendix A – Home Page

The screenshot shows the homepage of the PPN-Info website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for 'מבוא' (Introduction), 'מידע להורים' (Information for parents), 'מידע לאנשי מקצוע' (Information for professionals), 'מאמרים' (Articles), 'משאבים' (Resources), 'אודות' (About), and 'צור קשר' (Contact). A search bar is located on the left. The main content area is divided into three columns. The left column has a section titled 'חדשות' (News) with a sub-section '3 יוני 2009' and an article 'הכרות עם החולת המסע האנושי'. The middle column has a section titled 'בחנות וברוכים הבאים!' (Welcome to the shop!) with an article 'בחנות וברוכים הבאים לאתר העברי הראשון בנושא פסיכולוגיה פנהגטלית ופרניטלית'. To the right of this text is an image of a fetus curled in a ball. The right column contains a 'הרשמה לרשימת חפוצה' (Sign up for newsletter) form. At the bottom, there is a footer with copyright information and a Creative Commons license.

www.ppn-info.net

Appendix B – Introduction to PPN

The screenshot shows the homepage of the PPN website. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links: "מבוא", "מידע להורים", "מידע לאנשי מקצוע", "מאמרים", "משאבים", "אודות", and "צור קשר". The main content area is titled "מבוא" (Introduction) and features a central image of a woman holding a globe. The text on the page is in Hebrew and discusses the field of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology. At the bottom, there is a footer with copyright information and a Creative Commons license.

פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵהנְטָלִית ופְּרִינְטָלִית
Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

הקלד מילות חיפוש

מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לאנשי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | צור קשר

מבוא

תחום חדש ומרתק מתפתח בפסיכולוגיה בשלושים השנים האחרונות - פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵהנְטָלִית ופְּרִינְטָלִית - Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology.

לפסיכולוגיה פְּרֵהנְטָלִית ופְּרִינְטָלִית פוטנציאל אדיר לשנות את העולם משום שהיא נותנת לנו פרספקטיבה חדשה על עוברים וילודים ומציעה דרכים חדשות להיות עם תינוקות ולקבל את פניהם.

מהי פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵהנְטָלִית ופְּרִינְטָלִית? כיצד התפתחה? מיהם מייסדיה העיקריים? מה העקרונות המנחים שעמחן ממנה? על כל אלו, ניתן לקרוא במדור זה.

מבוא

« המדרה
« היסטוריה
« המייסדים
« 12 עקרונות מנחים

דף הבית | מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | חדשות | צור קשר

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ממוקד לציפיה בבריסונט 7 Internet Explorer או FireFox 2 ומעלה

<http://ppn-info.net/he/מבוא/>

Appendix C – Definition of PPN

פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵנָטָלִית וּפְרִינָטָלִית

Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

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הקלד מילות חיפוש

חפש

מבוא

מידע להורים

מידע לאנשי מקצוע

מאמרים

מסאבים

אודות

צור קשר

מבוא

« הגדרה

« היסטוריה

« המייסדים

« 12 עקרונות מסויים

הגדרה

מהי פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵנָטָלִית וּפְרִינָטָלִית (Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology)?

משמעות המילה "פרֵנָטָלִית" היא "טרם-לֵלֶת" ומשמעות המילה "פְּרִינָטָלִית" היא "קֵב־לֵלֶת" (שקשור לפרק הזמן המוקדם ללידה, לפני ואחריה). התקופה הפרֵנָטָלִית והפְּרִינָטָלִית בהתפתחות האדם כוללת את מועד ההפרייה, ההריון ותקופת הניקוט המוקדמת.¹

פסיכולוגיה פרהנטלית ופרינטלית בוחנת את ההשלכות הפסיכולוגיות של החוויות שאנו חווים בתקופה מוקדמת זו. בבסיס התחום עומדת ההכרה שהחוויות המוקדמות הללו בחינם, בייחוד חוויות טראומטיות, משפיעות באופן משמעותי על ההתפתחות הפסיכולוגית שלנו בעתיד ומשחקות תפקיד בעיצוב האישיות.²

פסיכולוגיה פרהנטלית ופרינטלית היא תחום מחקרי וגם גישה טיפולית.

תחום מחקר, פסיכולוגיה פרהנטלית ופרינטלית הנה מולטידיסציפלינרית (רב-תחומית). היא מאגדת מחקרים בתחום ה"התקשרות" (Attachment) והפסיכולוגיה הקלינית וכן מחקרים בתחומים כמו אמבריולוגיה (חקר העובר), נירוביולוגיה (חקר הביולוגיה של מערכת העצבים והמוח) ונולוגיה מולקולרית.³ במטרה לבחון את ההשפעה המעצבת של אותן חוויות ראשוניות על חינם.

נגישה טיפולית, פסיכולוגיה פרהנטלית ופרינטלית הנה אינטגרטיבית (משולבת). היא משלבת טכניקות טיפוליות חדשניות עם גישות טיפוליות מסורתיות בפסיכולוגיה כמו פסיכודינמיקה וגשטלט, והגישות הקוגניטיביות-ההומניסטיות-אקספטנציאליסטיות והסומטיות.^{3,4}

ניתן לשלב את הגישה הפרהנטלית והפרינטלית בטיפול פרטני או במסגרת טיפול קבוצתית² ופסיכותרפיים פרהנטלים ופרינטלים משלבים גישה זו בטיפול בתנוקות, ילדים, מתבגרים, מבוגרים ומשפחות.⁵

בבסיס הגישה הפרהנטלית ופרינטלית הטיפולית עומדת הנחת היסוד, שמקר משחקות האדם בחוה טפון בחוויות מהתקופה הפרהנטלית או הפרינטלית בחינם. על מנת לפא את בעיות החוה יש לחשוף ולהביא למועד את הקשר שלהם לתקופה הראשונית, תוך עיבוד המטען הרגשי הקשור בזכרונות העבר הטראומטיים.⁴

1. Emerson, W. (1989). Psychotherapy with infants and children. *Pre- and Peri-Natal Psychology Journal*, 3(3), 190-217.

2. Glenn, M. (2002). The use of body-centered psychotherapy in working with prenatal and perinatal imprints within a group context. *Proceedings, 3rd United States Association*.

3. *Body Psychotherapy Congress, June, 2002*.

4. Lyman, B. (2005). *Prenatal and perinatal psychology: An integrative approach*. A streaming video. Santa Barbara Graduate Institute, Santa Barbara, CA.

5. Lyman, B. (2007). *Prenatal and birth memories: Working with your earliest experiences to help your life today - a workbook for clients, a practice manual for clinicians*. Santa Barbara, CA: Santa Barbara Graduate Institute Publishing.

7. Santa Barbara Graduate Institute (2007). *What is prenatal and perinatal psychology?* Academic catalog for the entering class of 2007. Santa Barbara, CA.

* מקור התמונה: Kevin Curtis/Science Photo Library

דף הבית | מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לנעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | מסאבים | אודות | חדשות | צור קשר

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מומלץ לצייה ברוסות 7 Internet Explorer או Firefox 2 ומעלה

http://ppn-info.net/he/מבוא/מהי_פסיכולוגיה_פרהנטלית_ופרינטלית/

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Appendix D – History of PPN

[http://ppn-info.net/he/מבוא/היסטוריה של פסיכולוגיה פרהנטלית פרינטלית](http://ppn-info.net/he/מבוא/היסטוריה_של_פסיכולוגיה_פרהנטלית_פרינטלית)

Appendix F – 12 Guiding Principles

פסיכולוגיה פְּרִינְטָלִית וּפְרִינְטָלִית
Parental and Perinatal Psychology

מבוא | סידור להורים | סידור לאנשי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | צור קשר

הקדמה | מילות חיפוש | עמוד

www.ppn-info.net

12 עקרונות מנחים

במסגרת להנחות הורים ואנשי מקצוע ליוני נקודת תמיכה אופטימלית עבור תינוקות ומשפחותיהם, ד"ר אורן מרז' וד"ר מרטי ג'ון פרווה 12 עקרונות מנחים על בסיס הממצאים הקליניים והמדעיים שיבאו מעטן ענף הפסיכולוגיה הפרנטינלית והפרנטינלית במשך 30 השנים האחרונות.

להלן 12 עקרונות מתוך כריז עמדה¹ שרובם:

- 1. התקופה הראשונה**
התקופה הראשונה לתחלופות אנושית מתיישבת בטרום ההתנהגותית ולמרחק שנת החיים הראשונה לאחר הלידה. זהו הזמן הקריטי ליצירת יסודות קונטנטלל נמוכה המהירה: פיות, רגשות, מנטליה, כן אישיות והתנהגות.
- 2. זרימה טובה (Blueprints)**
לאנחות היסוד שלם ולדרך שיבה או זרימה בטלם עם עצמות עם אחרים יסודות בסיסים אלה אינם מודעים, ולכן ניתן לצפות בהם אצל תינוקות, והם שיערים את הדרך. יתכן גם מעטם להיות כל היום. דפוסי ליה לא מודעים אלה מנצבים את כל ההיבטים והולכים להיות בעלי השפעה מעמיקה או מחלישה על חייו.
- 3. דרך ההתפתחות**
ההתפתחות האנושית היא רצף אחד המסך מתקופה הפרנטינלית אל תוך החיים שאחרי הלידה. דפוסי אופטימליים נובעים על ידידות הפרנטינלית והתנהגותית הלידה. ניתן לצפות לשינויים אופטימליים לנולד, למימוש משיבותי ולסדר עמדות, קולו התפתחותי המות, אסילוגיה רגשית יסודות נעמי, כאשר קיימים תנאים אופטימליים במהלך התקופה שלפני ההתנהגותית. הוריות, הולדה והשגחה האופטימלית לזמן יסודות אופטימליים להקשרות חיבתה ולמערבות יחסים בריאות צפויים, כאשר מערכת החושים הן אופטימלית במהלך התקופה שלפני ההתנהגותית, במהלך ההריון, בחיית הלידה ובשנה הראשונה לחייו.
- 4. מנטליזציה וניחוח**
בני אדם נבנים בעלי מודעה מודעת, בעלי כושר חישה ומחשבת נעמי, אסיל בתקופה הראשונה ביותר. בחייה כבני אדם, אנו שאנשים לביטוי יחדיו ויחדיו מלאה ומלאה פנימית. דרך מילד זה הוא אש פנימה ונעמי וממשיח חיים בהתפתחותו האנושית. ממוחלת הורים, עשויים להיות, מתקשרים לאלמים, נודדים בשנת הלידה לתקופה חושית, נפגית, ולקשרות על-חשיבה.
- 5. מעורבות יחסית**
ההתפתחות האנושית מתיישבת כולן ההתחלה בתוך מערכת יחסים, והקשרים האנושיים והסביבה משפיעים משקוף על איכות ההתפתחות של התינוק בכל הבעיה. קולו דרטי הורים, התינוק הוא מקומם שיתוף שמינטי הוא מודע. עבור התינוק, מערכת היחסים של האב או אן הוא עם האם והתינוק מהווה חלק בלתי נפרד מייסודות חייו. האנשים, וחיות לביטוי האופטימליים. כל מערכת יחסים אנושית עם האם, התינוק הוא, התינוק הוא, התינוק הוא אישיות משפיעה על איכות חייו המתקדם על-בית התפתחותי לחייו. מערכת יחסים ממוחלת, אהובת ונדיבות חיובית לעצמי יסודות ראשונים אופטימליים.
- 6. צרכים מולדים**
הערך החיבורי, בטיחות, ביטחון, באהבה והנחה, בתחושה שאנו רשאים, מעורבים ותמיכים ענימי יחדיו. מוטו בני אדם הוא להישאף לחיים. היענות לביטוי אלה יבדית מבינה מתמדת, תמונת ההתפתחות אופטימלית.
- 7. תקשורת**
תינוקות אינם חולמים לתקשר ולהפסיק קשר. התייחסות היענות לתקופה נודדך שמבדות את יכולתו הרב-צדדית לתקשר, תמונת ההתפתחות האופטימלית ונשלמות החליטות.
- 8. הקשר הבדידי-אם-תינוק**
כיוון שיש אופטימלית של הקשר, כן הוא לתקופה, הקשר הדדי, ביניהם במהלך ההריון, הלידה, ותקופת התינוקות עשומים בראש סדר הדינמיות.
- 9. הקשרות לאמו (Bonding)**
ההריון וההריון הם התקופות האופטימליות לקשרים קרובים עם התינוק, והוא, והם יזערים דפוסי ליה בעלי השלמות לזמן החיים. התוצאה הטובה ביותר של הקשר, כן אש לתקופה מתקבלת כאשר האם והיא עשומת. תמונת התחילך הלידה הטובה ביותר היא-היא-היא עם הענות טובה מייסודות לביטוי כל הפעולה לקשר אם-תינוק ולתגובת הדיד, ביניהם, אם נבליצים להפיר את התקופה מתאם, יש לעודד מעט קשר רציפים של האב עם התינוק. תמונת מערכת יחסים עם האב אינה מופיעת, כאשר מתקשרים עם התינוק יסודות ואנשי התחילך הלידה מתוך ביטחון התקופה להתפתח. נגמי שקורה ולהעמיק את זדורת האירועים.
- 10. התרת קשיים ונרצח**
פתיח ויפסי של קפליקטים מתגבר והוא, טרום נבניות המשפיעות על איכות החיים של כל רבני ההתפתחות. מוטו בני אדם הוא להישאף לחיים. התגובות והתפתחות אלה יבדית מבינה מתמדת, תמונת ההתפתחות אופטימלית.
- 11. דפוסי לא מודעים**
פנימיות לא פתוחות או תמיכה וחיות לא אופטימליים שאתחיל במהלך ההתנהגות, ההריון, הלידה ובשנה הראשונה לחייו. קולו הלידה והתפתחות דפוסי בעלי השפעה מחלישה. אלו יבואו ליד, כיבוש בהתפתחות של קניות בריאות, כיוון מות, קשיים, במוח, נעמי, הפרעות הקשורות, קשי למהרה ולקיים אחרים למרחק מעל החיים.
- 12. חשיבות הקשיות**
דפוסי מחלישים אלה משים מתחילת הלידה של הפתיח, של ההריון וההריון, בתוך מערכת הדיד, תמונת מערכת יחסים מנמי, אישי קשיות אנושית, בסביבתיות ראשונה (פרנטינלית ופרנטינלית) מובילים להיות את הדפוסי הללו לעמוד ולענות, ללדים, להורים ולמבוגרים. דפוסי ראשונים והחלישים בדפוסי מעמי-חיים, ככל על, כאשר הורים מראים כענות לא פתוחות מתקופת ההריון ולידה, לידים מודעים מתוך מכלי.

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לידה התנהגות נבנית

* תרגום אנגלית לעברית, מור נוי (ממחנה נפסיכולוגיה פרנטינלית ופרנטינלית) סידור הלידה (2009)
לקבל, יפסי סול (ממחנה) יפסי סול (ממחנה) נפסיכולוגיה פרנטינלית ופרנטינלית.

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McCarty, W. A., & O'Brien, M. A. (2009). Investing in Human Potential: From the Beginning of Life: A Keynote to Maximizing Human Capital/Primary psychology: Bridging the divide of early development. Retrieved from <http://www.naturalfamilylinking.org>

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מחשב: עברית, דפוס: 7 Internet Explorer 7

<http://ppn-info.net/he/30/מבוא/>

Appendix G – Information for Parents

פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵה־נָטְלִית וּפְרִינָטְלִית
Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

הקלד מילת חיפוש

מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לאנשי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | צור קשר

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מידע להורים

ממנאים קליניים ומחקרים בתחום הפסיכולוגיה הפרהנטלית והפרינטלית שופכים אור חדש על הורות. כי הורות אינה מתחילה עם הלידת התינוק אלא הרבה לפני. במהלך ההריון עצמו, יש הטוענים, אמיל טורם ההפרייה. כיצד ניתן להתכונן להריון? כיצד משפיעים מצבה הרגשי של האם ומערכת החיסים שלה עם האב על העובר? אילו השלכות יש לבריאות האם ולאורח חייה במהלך ההריון על העובר? האם העובר מסוגל ללמוד ברחם? האם יש לו יכולת לזכור חוויות מהחיים ברחם? האם יש קשר בין מצבה הרגשי של האם לבין לידה מוקדמת? במדור זה, ניתן לקבל תשובות לשאלות אלו וכן לקבל מידע אודות סדנאות וחוגים להורים שברוך.

מידע להורים

- « בריאות לפני ההריון והכנה להריון »
- « בריאות ואורח חיים בהריון והסלכותיה »
- « הורות בהריון »
- « התייחסו המדרס שטרם מולד »
- « לידה »
- « סדנאות וחוגים »

דף הבית | מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לנעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | חדשות | צור קשר

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מומלץ לצייה בבראונט 7 Internet Explorer או Firefox 2 ומעלה

http://ppn-info.net/he/מידע_להורים/

Appendix I – Your Amazing Unborn Child

The screenshot shows a Hebrew website with a purple header. The main title is "כנהגות ופריונות" (Fertility and Pregnancy). The page layout includes a search bar at the top left, a navigation menu, and a main content area with multiple columns of text. There are several small images interspersed within the text, including a diagram of a fetus, a close-up of a person's face, and a medical scan. The text is in Hebrew and appears to be an informational article.

<http://ppn-info.net/he/מידע להורים/התינוק שטרם נולד>

Appendix J – Classes and Workshops

The screenshot shows the website for 'מדע להורים' (Parenting Science) under the umbrella of 'פסיכולוגיה פרינטיאלית ופרניטלית' (Perinatal and Perinatal Psychology). The page is titled 'מדע להורים' and contains the following content:

- Header:** Includes a search bar, navigation links (מבוא, מידע להורים, מידע לאנשי מקצוע, מאמרים, משאבים, אודות, צור קשר), and the website logo.
- Left Sidebar (מדע להורים):**
 - « בראות לפני ההריון והנכנה להריון »
 - « בראות ואורח חיים בהריון והסלכותיה »
 - « הרות בהריון »
 - « התנסה המדרס שטרם מילד ליה »
 - « סדנאות וחוגים »
- Main Content (מדע להורים):**

מעטפת ההולדה שואפת לקדם את החזון של התפתחות אנושית ורווחה בשלבי החיים הראשונים והמשמעותיים ביותר בחיי אדם: תקופת ההריון של האם והעובר, שעת הלידה והשנים הראשונות לחיים.

מעטפת ההולדה מקיימת פעילות לזוגות לפני ובמהלך ההריון, לפני הלידה ולאחריה. הפעילות אלו כוללות:

 - מפגשים לזוגות כהננה להריון, **בוע לפני הבן**
 - מפגשי עזרה לזוגות עם המידע לזמן ההריון.
 - קורסי הכנה ללידה, **פעמי לידה**.
 - מפגשי **נולדו חברים** עם ההורים הצעירים והתנוקות לאחר הלידה.

מטאנת חיים, פעמי לידה ומלוד הריון הן פעילויות המתקיימות בסופי שבוע.

אנו מאמינות שלקראת שנים מהותיים כדי לחשוב לעצור את המרוץ, להאט את הקצב, אפילו לזמן קצר, על מנת להשתדל לטווח שיקולם חזוי כאשר אנו מתכננים לקבל את פני החיים החדשים.

מנחות ומנהלות:
מר גור, מתמחה בפסיכולוגיה פרנטיאלית ופרניטלית (SBC), קליפריניה, מפתחת תכנים וסדנאות להורים שברוך.
אירית דתן, מילדת, מדריכת הכנה ללידה ומלווה זוגות לאחר לידה.

לפרטים והרשמה:
 בטלפון: 050-7444029, 04-6619189
 בדוא"ל: holads@gmail.com
- Footer:**

דף הבית | מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לנעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | חזרות | צור קשר

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מומלץ לציפה בבראזר Internet Explorer 7 או Firefox ומעלה

http://ppn-info.net/he/מדע_להורים/סדנאות_וחוגים/

Appendix L – Workshops and Conferences

The screenshot shows the website for Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology (PPN) in Israel. The header includes the logo and navigation menu. The main content area features a section titled "סדנאות קורסים וימי עיון" (Workshops, Courses, and Seminars). A specific announcement for a workshop titled "המרכז הקליני הבין-תחומי באוניברסיטת חיפה" (The Interdisciplinary Clinical Center at Haifa University) is displayed. The announcement includes details about the workshop's focus on perinatal loss, dates (October 17-19, 2009), location (Haifa), and contact information (Dr. Ilan Ilan, ilan@univ.haifa.ac.il, 04-8288622/3).

מידע לאנשי מקצוע

הקלד מילת חיפוש

פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵנָטָלִית וּפְרִינָטָלִית
Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לאנשי מקצוע | מאמרים | מסאבים | אודות | צור קשר

סדנאות קורסים וימי עיון

סדנאות

המרכז הקליני הבין-תחומי באוניברסיטת חיפה יקיים במהלך חודש יוני סדנה ייחודית בת שלושה מפגשים בנושא פסיכולוגיה פרהנטלית. הסדנה מיועדת לאנשי מקצוע ותעסוק בקשר הרגשי שבין ההורים לעובר והאמצעים לפתחו. מבין הנושאים שיידונו:

- * ההתפתחות הפיזית והרגשית של העובר
- * העובר ולמד לתקשר
- * משמעות של פנטזיות וחששות לגבי התפתחות העובר
- * ביצוע שלים מחוץ בין אירועי חיים מליחצים לבין העובר
- * מהעובר שהייתם לעובר שלנו
- * מההורות שהייתה לנו להורים שבהיה
- * חיזוק הקשר בין ההורים לעובר

הסדנה מתקיימת במרכז הקליני הבין-תחומי באוניברסיטת חיפה, בתאריכים 15.6.09, 17.6.09, 22.6.09, 29.6.09 ב"ב, בין השעות 17:30 - 20:00.

לפרטים והרשמה:
דוא"ל: ilan@univ.haifa.ac.il
טלפון: 04-8288622/3

קורסים

המרכז הישראלי לרפואת נון-ג'נז
מציג קורס סמסטרואלי למטפלים בשם
"מעט העצמי - רפואי טראומות טרום לידה ולידה".
הקורס סוּמַח בפי תמיכת תפיסת הודמנות
לחזור לשלב טרום הלידה והלידה של
עצמם נמקור למציאת דרך לחיפוי העצמי.
מנחה: רות בן-אשר MA
לפרטים נוספים

דף הבית | מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לנעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | מסאבים | אודות | חדשות | צור קשר

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מומלץ לנפיה בבראות 7 Internet Explorer או Firefox 2 ומעלה

http://ppn-info.net/he/מידע_לאנשי_מקצוע/סדנאות_קורסים_וימי_עיון

Appendix M – Articles

The screenshot shows the website for Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology (PPN-Info). The header includes the site name in Hebrew and English, a search bar, and a navigation menu with links for 'מבוא' (Introduction), 'מידע להורים' (Information for parents), 'מידע לאנשי מקצוע' (Information for professionals), 'מאמרים' (Articles), 'משאבים' (Resources), 'אודות' (About), and 'צור קשר' (Contact). The main content area is titled 'מאמרים' and lists three articles:

- ההשפעות הרגשיות והנפשיות של לידה בניתוח קיסרי על היילוד
פורסם ע"י אימי שפירא, בתאריך 28.04/2009
- מהמנתם של זכונות לידה בהיפנוזה
פורסם ע"י אימי שפירא, בתאריך 21.04/2009
- תדאפיה סומאטוהפסית
פורסם ע"י אימי שפירא, בתאריך 21.04/2009

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<http://ppn-info.net/he/מאמרים/>

Appendix N – Resources

הקלד מילת חיפוש

פסיכולוגיה פרהנטילת ופרינטילת
Pre-natal and Perinatal Psychology

מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לאנשי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | צור קשר

www.ppn-info.net

משאבים

מחפשים פסיכותרפיסט/ת המשלבת השקפה פרהנטילת ופרינטילת בעבודתה/ת? מעוניינים לקבל מידע אודות ספרים ותב"ע עת בן/ת?

איפה ניתן ללמוד פסיכולוגיה פרהנטילת ופרינטילת? אילו אתרים קיימים ברשת בנושא? במדור זה תקבלו תשובות לשאלות אלו.

מסדיר נשות ואנשי מקצוע
ספרות מומלצת
כתבי עת
קישורים מומלצים
לימודי המסך

דף הבית | מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לנעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | חדשות | צור קשר

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מונחל לציפיה בגרסאות 7 Internet Explorer או 2 Firefox ומונחל

<http://ppn-info.net/he/משאבים/>

Appendix O – Professionals' Directory

פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵה־וּפְרִינְטָלִית
Perinatal and Perinatal Psychology

מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לאנשי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | צור קשר

משאבים

- « מדריך נשות ואנשי מקצוע
- « ספרות מומלצת
- « כתבי עת
- « קטיורים מומלצים
- « לימודי המסך

מדריך נשות ואנשי מקצוע

נשות ואנשי מקצוע

שם	הכשרה	טלפון	דוא"ל	אתר בית
טל ורמון	מנחי סדנאות נשימה מודעת (ריברסינג)	052-2897824 (בת) 052-8566947 (טל)		
יקב קרביצ'אק	פסיכולוג קליני	052-8430902		
רחלם חזנוב	רופא נשים - מייל, מומחך בלידה הפטונומי	03-9347377		
רות ג. אשכ	פסיכולוגית קלינית מטפלת IMAGO מוסמכת מטפלת בטרואמות בשיטות SE ו-EMDR מטפל במים בשיטות Watsu, WaterDance & Jahara	054-4925903		

מרכזים

שם	טלפון	דוא"ל	אתר בית
המרכז הישראלי לפואת-הגוף	03-5495149		
המרכז הקליני הבין-תחומי באוניברסיטת חיפה	04-8268622/3		
"להיולד נוחש"	052-8566947 (טל)		
מעטפת החוליה	04-6619189		

דף הבית | מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לנעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | חדשות | צור קשר

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מומלץ לצייה בבראות 7 Internet Explorer או Firefox 2 ומעלה

http://ppn-info.net/he/מקצוע/אנשי_מקצוע/

Appendix Q – Journals

פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵנָטָלִית וּפְרִינָטָלִית
Perinatal and Perinatal Psychology

www.ppn-info.net

מבוא
מידע להורים
מידע לאנשי מקצוע
מאמרים
משאבים
אודות
צור קשר

משאבים

- « מדריך נשות ואנשי מקצוע
- « ספרות מומלצת
- « כתבי עת
- « קישורים מומלצים
- « לימודי המסך

כתבי עת

<p>Journal of Prenatal & Perinatal Psychology and Health</p>	<p>כתב העת של האיגוד האמריקאי לפסיכולוגיה פּרֵנָטָלִית וּפְרִינָטָלִית (APPPAH) לפרטים</p>	
<p>International Journal of Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology and Medicine</p>	<p>כתב העת של האיגוד האירופאי לפסיכולוגיה פּרֵנָטָלִית וּפְרִינָטָלִית (ISPPM) לפרטים</p>	
<p>Journal of Reproductive and Infant Psychology</p>	<p>כתב העת של החברה הבריטית לפיריון ופסיכולוגיה של הפגנט לפרטים</p>	
<p>Journal of Regression Therapy</p>	<p>כתב העת של האיגוד הבינלאומי למחקר ותרופיה רג'רסיבית לפרטים</p>	
<p>Infant Mental Health Journal</p>	<p>כתב העת של הארגון העולמי לבריאות נפש הפגנט (WAIMH) לפרטים</p>	
<p>The Primal Health Research Newsletter</p>	<p>ניולטר (תוכן) בעריכתו של ד"ר מישל אודנט לפרטים</p>	

דף הבית | מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לבעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | חדשות | צור קשר

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מומלץ לעייה בגרסאות 7 Internet Explorer או Firefox 2 ומעלה

http://ppn-info.net/he/כתבי_משאבים/

Appendix S – Continuing Education

הקלד מילת חיפוש

פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵה־נָטְלִית וּפְרִינָטְלִית
Perinatal and Perinatal Psychology

מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לאנשי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | צור קשר

www.ppn-info.net

לימודי המשך

משאבים

- « מדריך נשות ואנשי מקצוע
- « ספרות מומלצת
- « כתבי עת
- « קטגוריות מומלצות
- « לימודי המשך

הראשון בעולם המקנה תארים מתקדמים בפסיכולוגיה קלינית ופסיכולוגיה ייעוצית עם התמחות בפסיכולוגיה פרהנטלית ופרינטלית או פסיכולוגיה נופית. המוסד מציע תכנית לימודים מיוחדת בהתנדבות אשר מאפשרת לאנשים מכל העולם להתמחות בתחומים אלו.

בניסה

ד"ר ונדי אן מקרת' היא פסיכותרפיוסטית העובדת מתוך המישה הפרהנטלית והפרינטלית. מקרת' עוסקת שנים בהוראה והייתה מהוגי Santa Barbara Graduate Institute ומייסדיו. במסגרת היותה של מקרת' ניתן להירשם לקורסי אינטרנט בנושא פסיכולוגיה פרהנטלית ופרינטלית שהיא פיתחה.

בניסה

דף הבית | מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לנעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | חדשות | צור קשר

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מומלץ לצייה בגרסאות 7 Internet Explorer או Firefox 2 ומעלה

http://ppn-info.net/he/משאבים/לימודי_המשך/

Appendix T – About

פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵהנָטָלִית וּפְרִינָטָלִית
Prenatal and Perinatal Psychology

הקלד מילות חיפוש

חפש

מבוא | מידע להורים | מידע לאנשי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | צור קשר

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אודות

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[קורות חיים - עברית](#)
[CV - English](#)

[לאתר הבית של אימי שפירא](#)

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מומלץ לצייה בגרסאות 7 Internet Explorer או Firefox 2 ומעלה

<http://ppn-info.net/he/אודות/>

Appendix U – Contact

הקלד מילת חיפוש

פסיכולוגיה פְּרֵהנְטָלִית וּפְרִינְטָלִית
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טופס יצירת קשר

* שם מלא:

* אימייל:

טלפון:

עיר:

כתובת:

* משא הפניה:

* הודעה:

אם טופס | שלח

שדות המסומנים ב-הינם שדות חובה

צור קשר

הנכם מוזמנים ליצור קשר, אשמח לענות על כל שאלה!

דוא"ר: amy@ppn-info.net

טלפון: 1-706-6594421 (ארה"ב)

ניתן גם לשלוח הודעה בטופס המשרף.

דף הבית | מגזין | מידע להורים | מידע לנעלי מקצוע | מאמרים | משאבים | אודות | חדשות | צור קשר

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http://ppn-info.net/he/צור_קשר/